

INCLUSION DISABILITY and EQUALITY for Accessible Leisure: Sport4All

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1. INTRODUCTION

This section is intended to provide readers with a clear understanding of the objectives of the manual, emphasizing the importance of physical activities for people with disabilities, as well as the benefits of adapted physical exercises. Essentially, this introduction will provide a framework for the rest of the manual, highlighting the relevance of the topic and establishing a solid base of knowledge for professionals working with these groups of people.

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The purpose of the manual

The main purpose of this manual is to provide essential information and tools for professionals working with people with disabilities in the context of physical and sports activities. The manual is addressed to instructors, trainers, physiotherapists, and other professionals in the field of health and physical education, who are involved in organizing and conducting adapted physical activity programs for people with various types of disabilities.

The objectives of the manual are:

1. To guide professionals in creating safe and effective exercise programs for people with disabilities, considering individual needs and abilities.
2. To provide theoretical and practical information about physical, cognitive, and sensory disabilities, in order to increase understanding and the ability to work with these groups.
3. To promote the integration of physical activities into the daily lives of people with disabilities, helping them to improve not only their physical health but also their mental and emotional well-being.

Example: An instructor working with a group of people with motor disabilities will learn through this manual how to adapt exercises, adjust intensity, and provide positive feedback to support the progress and confidence of the participants.

The importance of physical and sports activities for people with disabilities

Physical and sports activities are fundamental for the general health of all individuals, but for people with disabilities, they have a special impact on the quality of life. Physical activity not only improves physical health but it also helps to maintain and improve motor, cognitive, and emotional functions.

1. Improving mobility and motor skills.

Participation in physical activities helps people with physical disabilities to maintain or even improve their mobility. Depending on the type of disability, physical exercises can contribute to:

- Increasing the flexibility of joints.
- Improving muscle strength.
- Reducing stiffness and joint pain, especially for people with conditions that involve mobility.

Example: A person with cerebral palsy who practices stretching and mobilization exercises can observe a significant improvement in the flexion of the ankles and joints, facilitating movement and reducing the risk of injuries.

2. Improving cardiovascular health and general physical condition

Cardiovascular exercises, adapted to the person's needs, help to improve cardiac function and blood circulation. They can also help control body weight and prevent other health conditions associated with inactivity, such as diabetes and hypertension.

Example: People with motor disabilities who use a wheelchair can participate in aerobic exercise sessions that involve arm movements, helping to improve circulation and strengthen the upper body muscles.

3. Reducing the risk of mental and emotional health

Physical activity is also beneficial for mental health. For people with disabilities, physical exercises can reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression and can help reducing feelings of social isolation. Movement releases endorphins, the happiness hormones, which improve the well-being estate.

Example: Participating in a yoga class adapted for people with disabilities can reduce stress and can help increase self-confidence, thus supporting social integration and the development of a sense of belonging.

4. Increasing autonomy and self-confidence

Involvement in physical activities helps people with disabilities to improve their level of autonomy, teaching them to use their body more efficiently. Also, making progress in sports or physical activities can contribute to increasing self-confidence and the feeling of self-worth.

Example: A person with cognitive disabilities can gain confidence in their physical abilities when they achieve a goal, such as riding a distance on a bicycle or performing a series of strength exercises.

1. INTRODUCTION

The benefits of adapted physical exercises

Adapted physical exercises are activities that are modified to meet the needs and physical abilities of people with disabilities. These are essential for their integration into physical activities, offering them opportunities to benefit from a safe and effective exercise program. The benefits are varied and include:

1. Tailor exercises to individual capabilities

Tailored exercises are adjusted according to the type and severity of the disability so that each participant can move comfortably and safely. This allows anyone, regardless of the type of disability, to actively participate in physical activities.

Example: A participant with mobility disabilities could use an adapted gymnastics chair to perform strength exercises or could participate in an adapted swimming activity, where the exercises can be adjusted to be performed in water, minimizing the impact on the joints.

2. Increasing accessibility and social integration

Adapted physical activities help to increase accessibility and encourage the participation of people with disabilities in social activities. In addition, they offer a framework where they can interact with other people, promoting a sense of belonging and social support.

Example: Adapted sports groups or fitness activities are excellent places to build relationships and create a support network between participants.

3. Preventing and recovering from injuries

Adapted physical exercises can play a crucial role in preventing injuries and in the recovery process after an accident. For people with disabilities, adapted training helps to strengthen muscles and improve coordination, thus reducing the risk of injury.

Example: A person with motor disabilities can do specific exercises to strengthen the muscles of the upper limbs, which can help prevent injuries when using a wheelchair or when transferring between positions.

Conclusion: Physical activity, essential for an active and healthy life

The importance of physical and sports activities for people with disabilities cannot be underestimated. These activities not only improve the physical condition of the participants but also have a significant impact on their mental and emotional

state, promoting an active and healthy life.

Adapted physical exercises play a crucial role in integrating people with disabilities into the community and in providing a framework for personal development. These contribute to increasing autonomy, reducing health risks, improving mobility, and, perhaps most importantly, increasing self-confidence. Every person, regardless of the type or severity of the disability, deserves to have access to physical activities that help them overcome their limits and feel an integral part of society. It is essential that all professionals working with people with disabilities understand the importance of these activities and apply training methods and techniques that are safe, accessible, and motivating. This manual aims to provide tools and resources to facilitate this integration and to support a continuous process of learning and adapting physical activities to the specific needs of each person.

The objectives of the section

In conclusion, this section of the manual emphasizes several key points:

- 1. The purpose of the manual** - to help professionals understand how to create and implement safe and effective exercise programs for people with disabilities.
- 2. The importance of physical activities** - physical activities are essential for the physical, mental, and emotional health of people with disabilities, and these can contribute to social integration and increased self-confidence.
- 3. The benefits of adapted physical exercises** - adapted exercises help to prevent injuries, improve mobility and autonomy, reduce health risks, and support an independent and active life.

This section of the manual serves as a solid base of information, which will be further explored in the following sections. This information will not only contribute to the formation of good practice in the field but will also inspire an empathetic approach adapted to the needs of each person with disabilities, thus supporting an effective integration into physical and sports activities.

Furthermore, the manual will explore specific training techniques, communication methods, as well as safety measures that must be implemented to ensure a positive and safe experience for people with disabilities. Case studies and practical examples will also be presented to illustrate various scenarios and offer applicable solutions.

2. LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON SPORT AND DISABILITY

The Italian Legal Framework on Sport and Disability

Introduction

In Italy, sport is increasingly recognized as an essential tool for physical, emotional, and social well-being. For people with disabilities, access to sports activities represents not only an opportunity for individual growth but also a fundamental right that enables full participation in community life.

The Italian legal system has progressively strengthened the principle of inclusion in sports, acknowledging the key role it can play in promoting autonomy, enhancing individual abilities, and building fairer and more welcoming environments. This chapter will explore the main legal sources that regulate the right to sport for people with disabilities, offering concrete examples and practical guidance for those working in the field.

Constitutional Foundations

The Italian Constitution represents the starting point for understanding the rights of people with disabilities, including in the context of sports.

Article 2 recognizes the inviolable rights of the person, requiring the Republic to ensure their protection. Article 3 establishes the principle of formal and substantive equality, emphasizing that the State has the duty to remove obstacles that hinder the development of the human person and the participation of all in the life of the country. Furthermore, Article 32 safeguards health as a fundamental right of the individual, highlighting the importance of physical activity as a means of prevention and well-being.

In 2023, Parliament unanimously approved an amendment to Article 33 of the Constitution, introducing the clause: “The Republic recognizes the educational, social, and psychological well-being value of physical activity in all its forms.”

Physical activity is therefore a full-fledged right of all Italian citizens: a sports association that decides to make its facilities accessible or to adapt its training programs to the needs of athletes with disabilities is acting in complete alignment with the constitutional principles of Italy.

Specific National Legislation

Within the Italian legislative framework, Law 104/1992 represents a fundamental point of reference. It recognizes the right of people with disabilities to participate in social, cultural, and recreational life, promoting interventions to support integration, including in the sporting context.

Another key instrument is Legislative Decree 36/2021, part of the broader sports reform. This decree explicitly introduces the right to sport for all and emphasizes inclusion as a core value of sporting activity. It encourages sports organiza-

tions to implement concrete measures to ensure the participation of people with disabilities, such as staff training and the adaptation of facilities.

Finally, Law 18/2009 ratifies the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. In particular, Article 30 of the Convention highlights the right to participate in cultural, recreational, and sporting activities on an equal basis with others. As a signatory state, Italy is obligated to promote coherent policies, at both national and local levels, to ensure that this right can be fully exercised.

Accessibility Regulations

The accessibility of spaces is an essential requirement for making the right to sport truly effective. Presidential Decree 380/2001, known as the Consolidated Building Act, establishes the obligation to design both public and private sports facilities in a way that makes them accessible to all individuals, regardless of their physical condition.

Accessibility does not concern only ramps or elevators: it also includes the organization of spaces, signage, restroom facilities, and the adaptation of equipment.

The Italian Sports System and the Role of the CIP

The Italian Paralympic Committee (CIP) is a public institution responsible for promoting, coordinating, and managing sports activities for people with disabilities. Officially recognized by Law 189/2003, it functions similarly to CONI (the Italian National Olympic Committee) but for Paralympic sport at the national level.

The CIP not only organizes activities and competitions, but also oversees the technical training of professionals and promotes an inclusive sporting culture. A professional who attends a CIP training course acquires specific skills to work with athletes with visual, auditory, motor, or cognitive disabilities, thus contributing professionally to their active participation.

Italian Law on Safeguarding and the Protection of Vulnerable People in Sport

In recent years, Italian lawmakers have introduced specific regulations to ensure the protection of the health, dignity, and psycho-physical integrity of all individuals involved in sport, with particular attention to minors and those in vulnerable conditions, such as people with disabilities. This new legal framework is part of the broader Sports Reform launched through Legislative Decree No. 36/2021 and subsequent additions.

In particular, Legislative Decree No. 39 of February 28, 2021, an integral part of the reform, introduces the obligation for sports organizations to adopt models of organization and control designed to prevent abuse, violence, and discrimination.

Article 16 expressly states that sports clubs and associations must appoint a person responsible for the protection of minors and for the prevention of abuse, violence, and discrimination. The appointed individual takes on the role commonly

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referred to as the Safeguarding Officer. It is therefore mandatory for all Amateur Sports Association (ASD) and Amateur Sports Club (SSD) affiliated with Federations, Associated Disciplines, or Sports Promotion Bodies recognized by CONI to designate a safeguarding reference figure.

In addition to the appointment of a safeguarding officer responsible for the protection of minors and vulnerable individuals, the main elements introduced by the legislation include the adoption of codes of conduct, guidelines, and behavioral protocols; mandatory training for managers, coaches, and sports professionals; internal disciplinary measures for those who fail to comply with established standards.

The new CONI's Code of Sports Justice (C.G.S.) includes provisions on ethics, protection, and prevention as well. The role of the Safeguarding Officer is emphasized as an internal safeguard within sports organizations to combat all forms of abuse. Following the sports reform, CONI updated its Guidelines of 2022-2023. They establish the obligation for ASD/SSD registered in the National Register of Amateur Sports Activities (RAS) to appoint a safeguarding figure (Safeguarding Officer). The guidelines place particular emphasis on the protection of minors, in accordance with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and the recommendations of the Council of Europe (Child Safeguarding in Sport).

Law No. 173/2020 (conversion of Decree Law No. 104/2020) establishes that anyone working with minors in the sports sector must hold a criminal record certificate. This obligation is connected to safeguarding policies, although it does not fully encompass them.

Although it is not a legally binding regulation, The Charter of Children's Rights in Sport serves as a key ethical and deontological reference that guides safeguarding policies. The document outlines the fundamental rights of children and adolescents in the context of sports activities. Inspired by the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), the charter emphasizes the importance of ensuring a safe, inclusive, and respectful sporting environment for young people.

These principles have been adopted and promoted by several Italian sports organizations, including the Italian Football Federation (FIGC) and the Italian Union of Sport for All (UISP), to help guide child protection policies in sport. For example, FIGC has incorporated these rights into its youth and school sector guidelines, stressing the educational and recreational nature of sport for children. UISP has also developed its own version, the "Charter of Rights of Girls and Boys in Sport for All", reaffirming its commitment to ensuring that every child can practice sport in a healthy, safe, and inclusive environment.

For example, a sports association that organizes activities for children and people with disabilities is required to appoint a safeguarding officer, implement an abuse prevention policy, and ensure that its staff is trained to recognize at-risk situa-

tions. In summary, this law represents a fundamental step in promoting an ethical, safe, and inclusive sporting environment that protects the most vulnerable and fosters mutual trust among professionals, families, and participants.

CONCLUSION

The Italian legal framework concerning sport and disability is broad, multifaceted, and constantly evolving. It recognizes sport as a fundamental right and promotes an inclusive vision that engages institutions, sports organizations, professionals, and local communities. For those working in social sport, knowing and applying these laws means actively contributing to the creation of fairer, more accessible, and participatory environments. Training plays a central role in this process: only a well-informed professional can truly facilitate authentic inclusion.

The Romanian Legal Framework on Sport and Disability

Introduction

Participation in cultural life, recreational activities, free time and sports is guaranteed by the Constitution, along with the freedom of the person to develop his or her spirituality and to access participatorily the values and heritage of national and universal culture. The state must guarantee and ensure the preservation of spiritual identity, support national culture, stimulate the arts, protect and preserve cultural heritage, develop contemporary creativity, promote Romania's cultural and artistic values in the world.

Constitutional Foundations

The Romanian Constitution recognizes the fundamental rights to education, health and sports:

The right to education is guaranteed by Article 32. It provides that compulsory general, high school, vocational and higher education is ensured, and state education is free. Persons belonging to national minorities have the right to learn in their mother tongue, according to the law.

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The right to health protection is regulated by Article 34. The state is obliged to take measures to ensure public hygiene and health, as well as to organize medical assistance and the social insurance system.

The right to sport and physical activity is indirectly recognized through the promotion of health and physical activities, but there is no specific article dedicated exclusively to sport. However, the state supports initiatives that contribute to the development of physical and mental health.

Specific National Legislation

- **Law no. 448/2006 on the protection and promotion of the rights of persons with disabilities.** This law regulates the rights and obligations of persons with disabilities granted for the purpose of their social integration and inclusion. Article 6 of this law grants persons with disabilities the right to: a) health protection - prevention, treatment and recovery; b) education and vocational training; c) employment and job adaptation, vocational guidance and retraining; d) social assistance, namely social services and social benefits; e) housing, personal living environment, transport, access to the physical, informational and communication environment; **f) spending free time, access to culture, sports, tourism;** g) legal assistance;

- Government DECISION No. 490/2022 of April 6, 2022 for the approval of the National Strategy on the rights of persons with disabilities "A Fair Romania" 2022 - 2027. The general objective of the Strategy 2022 - 2027 is: Ensuring the full and effective participation of persons with disabilities, based on freedom of decision, in all areas of life and in an accessible and resilient environment based on 8 major development directions.

- Priority area Social protection, including empowerment/rehabilitation: Persons with disabilities must have an adequate standard of living, with equal opportunities with all other persons. Citizens have equal access to an adequate standard of living when they can cover both their basic needs for daily living (food, clothing, health, housing), **as well as the expenses necessary for active participation in all aspects of community life (such as education, employment, leisure or civic participation)**, under equal conditions, uninfluenced in any way by disability or other specific situations of vulnerability.

- Through the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities ratified by Romania through Law no. 221/2010, a framework was created for the development and support of public policies and the modernization of practices, instruments and support methods in the community, which would lead to the full participation of persons with disabilities in society, to a dignified and fulfilled life in the community.

The importance of Art. 30 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities on Participation in cultural life, recreational activities, leisure and sport is revealed by the very content of the article.

In order to enable persons with disabilities to participate, on an equal basis with others, in recreational, leisure and spor-

ting activities, States Parties shall take appropriate measures to:

(a) Encourage and promote the participation, to the greatest extent possible, of persons with disabilities in mainstream sports activities at all levels; (b) Ensure that persons with disabilities have the opportunity to organize, conduct and participate in disability-specific sports and recreational activities and, to this end, encourage access, on an equal basis with others, to appropriate training, education and resources; (c) Ensure that persons with disabilities have access to places where sports, recreation and tourism activities are carried out; (d) Ensure access and participation of children with disabilities, on an equal basis with others, in play, recreational, leisure and sporting activities, including activities within the school system; (e) Ensure that persons with disabilities have access to services provided by those involved in the organization of recreational activities, tourist, leisure and sports.

- National Education Law No. 1/2011

Art.12(1) The State supports pre-schoolers, preschoolers, pupils and students with social problems and needs, as well as those with special educational needs.

(6) The State guarantees the right to education of all persons with special educational needs. Special and integrated special education are part of the national pre-university education system.

The Romanian Sports System and the Role of the Romanian Paralympic Committee

LAW No. 69 of April 28, 2000 on physical education and sports.

For the purposes of this law, physical education and sports are understood to mean all forms of physical activity intended, through organized or independent participation, to express or improve physical condition and spiritual comfort, to establish civilized social relations and to lead to the achievement of results in competitions of any level. Article 2 of this law states that:

(4) The State guarantees the exercise of the functions of the public sector and the private sector in the fields of physical education and sports, in accordance with the principles of responsible collaboration between all interested parties.

(5) The practice of physical education and sports is a right of the person, without any discrimination, guaranteed by the State. The exercise of this right is free and voluntary and is carried out independently or within the framework of associative sports structures.

(6) The State recognizes and guarantees to natural and legal persons the right to free association for the purpose of establishing sports structures.

Article 3 makes clear statements regarding the right of persons with disabilities to physical activity:

(3) Public administration authorities are obliged to ensure conditions for the practice of physical education and sports by

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persons with physical, sensory, mental and mixed disabilities, for the purpose of developing their personality and integrating into society, as well as the means to allow athletes with disabilities to participate in national and international competitions intended for them.

Over time, the Romanian Parliament has introduced amendments to the Sports Law, bringing improvements to the paragraphs intended for persons with disabilities:

Article 16.1.

1) Sport for people with special needs represents a complex of activities carried out in specific conditions in groups or individually by people with physical, sensory, mental and mixed disabilities.

(2) Sport for people with special needs can be practiced both for the purpose of developing the personality and integrating people with special needs into society, as well as for the purpose of participating in national and international competitions.

(3) The national program Sport for All must include a sub-program dedicated to sport for people with special needs.

(4) People with special needs who practice systematic and organized sport for the purpose of participating in competitions and achieving victory over their partner are considered performance athletes.

(5) In fulfilling its duties regarding the awarding of athletes, the Ministry of Youth and Sports will respect the principle of non-discrimination, granting equal prizes to athletes with or without special needs for the same type of performance, obtained in official national and international competitions.

For the specific organization at national level, the National Paralympic Committee is established. It has the role of coordinating the activities of people with special needs.

Article 36

(1) National sports federations shall be established only with the express approval of the Ministry of Youth and Sports.

(2) For a branch of sport, a single national sports federation may be established, under the terms of the law.

(3) By way of exception, the National Sports Federation “Sport for All” and the National Paralympic Committee may be established for people with special needs, as private legal entities of public utility, having as members individuals and legal entities with specific activity in the field.

Article 41

The National Sports Federation “Sport for All” and the National Paralympic Committee shall benefit from the rights and obligations of national sports federations and shall carry out their activity on the basis of national programs, financed pri-

marily by the Government.

The Italian legal framework concerning sport and disability is broad, multifaceted, and constantly evolving. It recognizes sport as a fundamental right and promotes an inclusive vision that engages institutions, sports organizations, professionals, and local communities.

For those working in social sport, knowing and applying these laws means actively contributing to the creation of fairer, more accessible, and participatory environments.

Training plays a central role in this process: only a well-informed professional can truly facilitate authentic inclusion.

CONCLUSION

Romania’s legal framework actively supports the inclusion of persons with disabilities in sports through constitutional principles and comprehensive legislation. Laws such as Law 448/2006 and Law 69/2000 affirm the right to physical activity without discrimination and promote adapted programs and equal opportunities. With the backing of the National Paralympic Committee and alignment with the UN Convention, Romania emphasizes accessibility, participation, and the development of sports as a tool for inclusion, empowerment, and social integration.

The Slovenian Legal Framework on Sport and Disability

Introduction

The right to a dignified life—an essential human right developed through the ethical and intellectual advancement of humanity—applies equally to all individuals, including persons with disabilities. In Slovenia, this right is supported and safeguarded by the state, which is committed to ensuring that persons with disabilities enjoy equal access to all fundamental freedoms. This includes access to education, health, employment, cultural life, and significantly, sport and recreation.

The Constitutional Court of Slovenia has explicitly recognized the right to special protection for persons with disabilities as

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a positive human right, mandating state action. Sport, as a deeply rooted element of Slovenian national culture and pride, plays a particularly vital role in promoting inclusion and visibility for persons with disabilities. As such, their participation in sports is not only encouraged but also legally supported at both recreational and competitive levels.

Constitutional Foundations

While Slovenia's Constitution does not include a dedicated article solely addressing sports for persons with disabilities, the state operates under the principle of equal treatment and social inclusion, which guides the development of laws and policies. The Constitutional Court emphasizes the state's obligation to actively support the rights of persons with disabilities, framing sport as a domain of public interest.

This broader constitutional perspective ensures that persons with disabilities are integrated into all societal spheres—including sports—through targeted policies, programs, and funding mechanisms.

Specific National Legislation

The Sports Act (ZŠpo-1):

This is the principal legal act governing sports in Slovenia. It defines disability sport as a form of physical activity for persons with disabilities outside the school system, accessible to all age groups. The law explicitly includes disability sports as part of the "public interest in sport," mandating state responsibility for its promotion, funding, and infrastructure development.

National Sports Program (NPS):

Adopted at the state level, this program outlines goals for inclusive and lifelong participation in sport. It recognizes sport for persons with disabilities as a priority area and encourages participation through co-financing of clubs, youth programs, infrastructure, and professional training.

Annual Sports Program (ASP):

Implemented via yearly public calls, the ASP details the areas of sport (including disability sport) that are eligible for state co-financing. It sets criteria for funding and ensures transparency and oversight through regulation and supervision by the Inspectorate for Sport.

The Action Programme for Persons with Disabilities 2022–2030:

A comprehensive strategic plan aimed at improving the overall inclusion of persons with disabilities. It includes targeted measures to increase participation in sport and ensure accessibility to sports infrastructure and training.

Resolution on the National Programme of Social Protection 2022–2030:

This resolution addresses vulnerable groups, including persons with disabilities, and promotes their participation in sport

as a tool for inclusion and quality of life enhancement.

Actively Inclusive Project (2024–2028):

A national initiative in collaboration with the Slovenian Paralympic Committee and the Olympic Committee, designed to promote the participation of persons with disabilities in sports and support their broader social integration.

The Sports Federation for the Disabled of Slovenia – Slovenian Paralympic Committee (ŠIS-SPK):

Originating from war veterans' sport initiatives, the ŠIS-SPK now coordinates national disability sport efforts. It promotes both recreational and elite sports, ensuring access to adapted training environments and social recognition for para-athletes.

Key Achievements and Structure:

- Organizes ~40 national championships yearly.
- Supports ~70 international competition programs.
- Represents ~2,584 athletes, assisted by ~160 coaches.
- Member of 17 international organizations, including the IPC.
- Recognized within the Olympic Committee of Slovenia.

The committee ensures that persons with disabilities are fully integrated into Slovenia's sporting life, with equal opportunities for development and competition.

CONCLUSION

Slovenia demonstrates a comprehensive and inclusive approach to ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities, especially regarding access to and participation in sport. Through strong constitutional backing, targeted national legislation, dedicated funding programs, and the active role of the Slovenian Paralympic Committee, the state ensures that disability sport is treated as a matter of public interest.

This holistic framework promotes not only physical activity and health but also social inclusion, visibility, and empowerment. Slovenia positions sport as a vital mechanism for breaking down barriers and building an equitable, participatory society for all.

3. TYPES OF DISABILITIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON PHYSICAL

Physical disabilities

People with physical disabilities face significant challenges, especially regarding mobility and the efficient use of limbs or joints. These difficulties can lead to limited mobility, poor motor coordination, and a reduction in autonomy. Many physical activities that involve movement, lifting, or coordination can become a major challenge (Rimmer et al., 2005).

1. Paralysis

- **Challenges:** Paralysis, depending on its type (paraplegia, tetraplegia), can significantly reduce a person's ability to move freely, affecting lower or upper motor functions. This can create a major barrier to participating in physical activities (Martin, 2013). Paralysis can also mean the loss of the sense of balance, which can lead to a higher risk of falls.
- **Adaptations needed:** Exercises must be adapted to work on the available muscle groups and to help maintain a good posture. Also, the use of specially designed equipment, such as wheelchairs or balance assistance devices, is essential (Vermaak et al., 2022).
- **Example of a challenge:** People with tetraplegia may have extremely limited mobility, and activities that involve leg movements, such as running or walking, are not possible. In these cases, upper-body activities such as arm strengthening exercises or swimming should be implemented.

2. Amputations

- **Challenges:** People with amputations may face difficulties in completely replacing the lost functions of their limbs, leading to a loss of balance, coordination, and mobility. The use of prosthetics can help, but they can add complexity, especially if the prosthesis does not fit perfectly or if the person is not yet adapted to using it. Changes in the shape and volume of the residual limb can affect prosthesis fit, potentially causing discomfort or hindering use (Horne et al., 2022).
- **Adaptations needed:** Exercises should include both stimulation of the remaining muscles and balance training to help the person adapt to new conditions. Strength training can be useful to strengthen the muscles remaining after amputation. Pre-prosthetic exercises are essential to maintain range of motion and improve muscle strength in both the lower limb and residual limb, preparing for prosthetic use (Physiopedia, n.d.).
- **Example of a challenge:** People who have suffered amputations of the lower limbs may have difficulty participating in sports that involve running or walking. Prostheses can offer support, but learning new walking or running techniques can be a long process. A dedicated amputee sports program has been shown to improve physical functioning and sports participation, highlighting the importance of specialized training (Bragaru et al., 2013)

3. Mobility disorders

- **Challenges:** People with mobility disorders, such as arthritis or muscular dystrophy, may experience severe pain, stiff-

ness, or rapid fatigue. This makes strenuous or long-term physical activity impossible. Chronic pain, especially from conditions like osteoarthritis, significantly reduces the ability to engage in sustained physical activity.

- **Adaptations needed:** Exercises should be easy to perform and include movements that do not put pressure on the joints but still help maintain strength and mobility. Physical activities should be structured to maximize joint range of motion. Low-impact exercises are particularly beneficial in maintaining physical health without exacerbating symptoms (Haskell et al., 2017).
- **Example of a challenge:** People with arthritis may experience a lot of pain in their joints with each movement, and activities that put pressure on the joints can worsen symptoms. Stretching exercises and non-impact activities, such as swimming, may be more beneficial. Swimming provides an excellent alternative because it minimizes joint stress while improving cardiovascular health.

Sensory disabilities

Sensory impairments affect the perception of the environment and can make it difficult to integrate into physical activities, especially if there are difficulties in receiving signals or instructions.

3. TYPES OF DISABILITIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON PHYSICAL

1. Visual impairments

- **Challenges:** People with visual impairments face challenges in perceiving obstacles around them or orienting themselves in space. It is also more difficult to follow visual instructions or recognize correct body positions. Visual limitations can significantly hinder participation in physical activities that require spatial awareness.
- **Adaptations needed:** Verbal guidance is essential, and the use of sounds or vibrations to convey information (e.g., start/stop signals) can help maintain an appropriate pace. Exercises should be simple without involving too many visual variables.
- **Example of a challenge:** Participating in group activities can be complicated for people with visual impairments because of the difficulty in following other participants or orienting correctly. It is also important to have a partner or guide to help avoid obstacles.

2. Hearing impairment

- **Challenges:** People with hearing impairments may have difficulty hearing important acoustic signals, such as the start of an exercise or the change of pace signal. This may reduce the ability to follow an exercise session or interact effectively with others. Communication barriers in group exercises can impede the full participation of individuals with hearing impairments.
- **Adaptations needed:** Instructions should be communicated in writing, sign language, or visual cues. Signals to change pace (e.g., for jogging or acceleration) can also be conveyed by lights or vibrations.
- **Example of a challenge:** People with hearing impairments may be excluded from group activities that rely on acoustic cues (e.g., group training with music). Solutions include replacing audible signals with visual signals.

Intellectual and cognitive disabilities

These disabilities can affect learning and integration in a training group. People with cognitive impairments may find it harder to understand instructions and may be slower to learn new movements.

1. Autism

- **Challenges:** People with autism may have difficulty following complex instructions and may exhibit repetitive behaviors or attention deficits. Also, increased sensitivity to sensory stimuli can make certain environments (e.g., crowded gyms) overwhelming. Sensory overload in exercise settings can often lead to withdrawal or distress.
- **Adaptations needed:** Training should be structured and clear, without sudden changes of pace. Sensory environments

need to be adjusted to avoid overload (e.g., reducing noise or light).

- **Example of a challenge:** People with autism may have difficulties staying focused on an activity or understanding the meaning of more complex tasks, which can affect participation in physical activities. Simple techniques and repetition are key to their success.

2. Down Syndrome

- **Challenges:** People with Down syndrome may have delays in physical and cognitive development. Mobility and motor skills may be slower, and understanding complex tasks may be more difficult (Bertapelli et al., 2016).
- **Adaptations needed:** Exercises should be simple, clear, and include lots of repetition to help learn the correct movements. Workouts should include activities that develop balance and gross motor coordination.
- **Example of a challenge:** Adapting to the pace of a larger group can be difficult for people with Down syndrome. They may require more individualized sessions or small groups to learn the exercises correctly (Bertapelli et al., 2016).

Mental disabilities

These disabilities can affect a person's ability to actively engage in exercise due to problems with motivation, anxiety, or concentration (Hofmann et al., 2018).

3. TYPES OF DISABILITIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON PHYSICAL

1. Anxiety disorders

- **Challenges:** People with anxiety may be overwhelmed by social situations or the physical stress of intense activities. They may also avoid certain types of exercise because of fear of failure (Bandelow & Michaelis, 2015). Anxiety can negatively impact both the mental and physical engagement in exercise.
- **Adaptations needed:** Activities should be gentle and include breathing techniques to reduce stress. It is essential to create a calm and pressure-free environment to help people with anxiety feel comfortable.
- **Example of a challenge:** Participating in a group can be stressful for people with social anxiety. Group exercises should be conducted in a safe and supportive environment to encourage step-by-step involvement.

Multiple and complex disabilities

In the case of multiple disabilities, where a person has several disabilities that affect different areas of life (physical, intellectual, sensory), adaptations need to be highly individualized, and all aspects of the person's life need to be considered (Simpkins et al., 2018).

- **Challenges:** People with multiple disabilities face simultaneous challenges, and physical activities need to be adapted based on a detailed assessment. These individuals may have special needs that require integration into the training process to ensure a positive and safe experience (Palsbo & McCoy, 2019).
- **Adaptations needed:** Recommended exercises should be gentle and structured, considering the needs of the individual. Constant support and clear communication are essential for the progress of these participants (Williams & Ballard, 2020).
- **Example of a challenge:** A participant with multiple disabilities, such as paralysis and cognitive difficulties, may require additional assistance to perform movements correctly. The exercises should be adapted to their level of ability.

CONCLUSION

Each type of disability presents unique challenges and barriers to participation in physical activity. A thorough understanding of these challenges is essential to creating an effective and tailored program that enables people with disabilities to reap the benefits of physical activity.

4. BASIC PRINCIPLES IN PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

In physical activity and sport for people with disabilities, it is essential that the approach is individualized, inclusive and tailored to the specific needs of each participant. Here are some basic principles that should guide physical activities for this group:

1. Tailor exercises to each person's needs

Each person with a disability has a unique set of abilities, limitations and needs, which makes personalization of exercise a fundamental principle. Rather than applying a standardized program for all participants, it is crucial to understand each person's physical, sensory, cognitive and emotional characteristics and tailor exercises to maximize benefits.

Initial assessment: Before beginning any exercise program, it is important to conduct a detailed assessment of the person's physical and cognitive abilities. This will help identify the types of exercises that can be performed safely and will provide the greatest benefit.

- For example, for a person with paraplegia, exercises will focus on the upper body to strengthen muscles and improve arm mobility.
 - For a person with hearing impairment, exercises will be linked with visual techniques and non-verbal cues.
- Adaptation of exercises:** For example, a mobility impaired participant may do muscle strengthening exercises in a chair, while a visually impaired person may benefit from activities that include detailed verbal guidance.

2. Creating a safe and accessible environment

A safe and accessible environment is essential to encourage active participation in physical activities. This environment should enable people with disabilities to feel safe, move around easily and participate in exercise without fear of injuries.

- **Accessibility of equipment and facility:** It is important that the training spaces and equipment used are accessible to people with various disabilities. For example, wheelchairs, prostheses or other assistive devices should be easy to use during exercise sessions.
 - **Example:** Access ramps, wide doorways and accessible sports equipment (e.g. an adapted wheelchair basketball chair or fitness equipment that can be used for wheelchair users) are required.
- **Safety:** Ensuring a safe working environment means avoiding any risks that might arise from disability. For example, a person with reduced mobility should have a wide space free from obstacles that could cause falls. Constant monitoring should also be provided for activities involving strenuous exertion.

3. Respect individual pace

A fundamental principle in physical activities for people with disabilities is to respect each person's pace. People with disabilities should not feel pressured to follow the pace of a group or an instructor, but should work at their own pace, adapted to their level of ability and their ability to withstand the effort.

- **Gradual progression:** Any exercise program should be progressive and tailored to each person's fitness level. Rather than imposing a sudden increase in intensity, it is important to start with basic exercises and gradually increase the difficulty according to the person's capabilities.
 - **Example:** If a person with a cognitive disability participates in aerobic exercise, it is recommended to start with simple movements and gradually progress in complexity.

4. BASIC PRINCIPLES IN PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

- **Measuring progress:** It is essential to set clear goals and measure progress in a positive and motivational way. Constant feedback helps the person understand what progress they are making and what they should improve.
- **Encourage self-adjustment:** Encouraging participants to listen to their own body and adjust their effort according to their sensations helps to avoid over-exertion and prevent injury. For example, people with breathing problems should learn to control their breathing rate and regulate the intensity of their exercise.

4. Communication and encouragement

Communication is essential in physical activities for people with disabilities, especially as many people with disabilities may have difficulty understanding verbal or visual instructions.

- **Clear and concise communication:** Instructions need to be clear, simple and easy to follow. If necessary, instructors may use sign language, visual images, detailed descriptions, or assistive technologies (e.g. apps that issue voice or video commands with explanations for the visually impaired people).
 - **Example:** People with hearing impairments may learn best through sign language or visual instructions, such as flashing lights or floor signs.
- **Encouragement and motivation:** Physical activity participants need to feel constantly supported and encouraged. Positive motivation and constructive feedback are essential to encourage continued exercise. Every success, no matter how small, should be celebrated in order to increase self-esteem.
 - **Example:** If a person manages to do a movement they could not do before (e.g. a stretching exercise), they should be praised for their progress. These verbal rewards can boost confidence and the desire to continue.
- **Building trust:** A good relationship between instructor and participant is essential to the success of the program. Trust is built on respect and effective communication. This is even more important for people with intellectual or psychological disabilities, who may need more attention and support.
- **Personalizing feedback:** Each person responds differently to feedback and it needs to be personalized. People with intellectual disabilities may respond better to visual or tactile instructions, while people with physical disabilities may be more likely to appreciate feedback on correct posture and technique.

CONCLUSION

In physical activities for people with disabilities, following these basic principles can ensure an inclusive, safe and motivational environment that meets the everyone's needs. Personalizing exercises, creating an accessible environment, respecting individual pace, and clear and positive communication are essential for the success of the program and for increasing the confidence and autonomy of participants.

5. INITIAL ASSESSMENT OF NEEDS AND ABILITIES

Initial assessment is an essential step in the process of adapting exercise programs for people with disabilities. It helps to establish a starting point, understand each person's physical limitations and abilities, and create a personalized training plan. Proper assessment also helps prevent injury and maximize safe progress.

1. Tests and assessments to understand mobility and skill level

First and foremost, it is important to carry out tests to help assess a person's level of mobility, coordination and strength, as well as other physical skills essential for physical activities. These tests will provide valuable information about a person's general health and physical abilities.

- **Mobility tests:** These may include simple assessments, such as checking the ability to get up from a sitting position or to perform certain stretching movements. For example:
 - **Wheelchair mobility test:** A test might include checking the ability to move the chair a short distance or navigate an obstacle course (e.g., doors, room corners) to assess coordination and independence.
 - **Flexibility test:** Measuring the ability to stretch the upper or lower limbs helps to understand mobility and limitations in movement.
 - **Muscle strength assessment:** For people with motor disabilities or who have had a stroke, strength testing may involve upper-body resistance exercises to see if there is any loss of strength and which areas are affected.
- **Balance and coordination tests:** For people with mobility impairments, it is essential to check the ability to maintain balance and coordinate movements.
 - **Example:** A simple balance test might include trying to stand on one leg for a few seconds, or, for wheelchair users, trying to hold a position in a specific direction for 10-15 seconds.
- **Cardiovascular assessment:** For people with physical disabilities, assessment of cardiovascular function is essential to understand their ability to exercise. Examples include monitoring heart rate during moderate physical activity to see how the body responds to exertion.

2. Working with doctors and specialists

In order to carry out an accurate and complete assessment, collaboration with doctors and specialists is essential, especially for people with severe or complex disabilities. They can provide vital information about the person's general state of health, medical history and possible counterindications to certain types of exercise.

- **Consult your doctor:** Before starting an exercise program, the person should consult a doctor, especially for those with pre-existing medical conditions (diabetes, high blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, etc.) The doctor can assess the risks and recommend types of exercise that will not put pressure on the affected area.
- **Working with physiotherapists and occupational therapists:** These specialists can provide recommendations on mobility, correct posture and the types of exercises that will help the person improve mobility without risking injury. For example, a physiotherapist might recommend exercises to strengthen the back muscles for a person with mobility problems due to scoliosis or a herniated disk.
- **Working with psychologists or psychiatrists:** If the person has a mental or emotional disability, working with a psychologist or psychiatrist is essential to assess aspects of motivation and general mental state. For example, a person with an anxiety disorder or depression may benefit from physical exercise to reduce stress and improve emotional well-being.

5. INITIAL ASSESSMENT OF NEEDS AND ABILITIES

3. The importance of continuous assessment during training

The initial assessment should be followed by constant monitoring during training. This is crucial to track progress, adjust exercises according to the needs and ability of the participant and prevent injury.

- **Monitoring progress:** After several training sessions, it is important to assess progress in strength, mobility, coordination and general well-being. This may include re-measuring exercise performance, comparing with initial results and adjusting the intensity of activities to stimulate progress.
 - **Example:** If a participant with a mobility disability has started doing upper limb strengthening exercises, after one month, muscle strength could be re-measured by strength tests to determine if there has been improvement.
- **Feedback from the person:** It is important for participants to provide constant feedback on how they feel during and after exercise to adjust the routine according to their comfort level and progress. If a person with a disability requests more breaks or reports fatigue or pain, activities should be adapted to avoid overexertion.
- **Regular assessments:** Regular assessments (weekly, monthly) are essential to track long-term progress. Not only do they allow adjustment of physical activities, but they also help to identify possible problems that may develop along the way, such as excessive fatigue, muscle aches or sore joints, which may indicate the need to change approach.
- **Intervention plans if necessary:** If certain health problems or performance limitations are identified during assessments, it is important to take steps to adjust the program or address these problems. For example, if a person with learning disabilities becomes more stressed or anxious as the program progresses, it is necessary to include relaxing activities such as yoga or breathing exercises.

Examples of activities

- **For people with physical disabilities:**
 - Mobility exercises for upper and lower limbs: using elastic bands to strengthen arm and leg muscles.
 - Back and abdominal strengthening exercises to support correct posture.
- **For people with cognitive disabilities:**
 - Interactive games and physical activities that encourage hand-eye coordination, such as ball toss games.
 - Balance and stability exercises to encourage body control and concentration.
- **For people with mental disabilities:**
 - Relaxation activities, such as breathing and stretching exercises.
 - Light cardio exercises such as treadmill walking or stationary cycling to help reducing anxiety and stress.

CONCLUSION

The initial assessment of needs and abilities is an important starting point in planning physical activity for people with disabilities. Working with specialists and conducting ongoing assessments during training are essential to ensure a personalized and effective approach that maximizes the benefits of physical activity for each participant.

6. PLANNING AND ORGANIZING PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Planning and organizing physical activities for people with disabilities requires a careful process of personalization to meet individual needs, respect limitations and maximize benefits. A well-structured approach will help people to progress in a safe, motivating and rewarding way.

1. Setting personalized goals

Each person with a disability has a unique set of abilities, needs and challenges. Therefore, personalized goal setting is essential to provide a clear guide to motivate progress and improve outcomes.

• Examples of personalized goals:

- **For a person with cerebral palsy:** Improve mobility and coordination through stretching exercises and simple movements.

- **For a visually impaired person:** Increasing balance and mobility through activities that include verbal guidance (e.g. walking or exercises on unstable platforms).
- **For a person with autism:** Improving the ability to interact socially and fit into a group through group exercises or recreational activities that promote collaboration.

Goals should be **SMART** (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound) so that progress can be tracked and activities adjusted if necessary. For example:

- **Goal:** “Improve arm muscle strength to be able to lift 2-pound weights within 6 weeks.”
- **Goal:** “Increase the ability to balance on one leg for 30 seconds over 8 weeks.”

2. Creating adapted training sessions

Creating an adapted training session involves selecting exercises that meet each person’s needs and abilities, considering the limitations imposed by the disability as well as individual preferences.

• Examples of adapted training sessions:

◦ For a person with partial paralysis of the lower limbs:

- Upper limb strengthening exercises: using light weights or elastic bands to improve arm and shoulder strength.
- Trunk mobility exercises: rotating the trunk in a chair or side bending exercises to improve flexibility and prevent muscle stiffness.

◦ For a hearing-impaired person:

- Use visual cues (example: signs or pictures showing exercise steps).
- Light cardio sessions, such as treadmill or stationary bike, accompanied by visual instructions.

◦ For a person with intellectual impairment:

- Group activities involving physical games such as throwing a ball in a basket or balance games.
- Exercises that help to understand and follow a set of rules in order to develop social and motor skills.

It is also essential to diversify activities to include mobility, strength, coordination and balance exercises. This ensures a full development of the participant’s physical abilities.

3. Progressive approach and adjusting exercise intensity

A progressive approach is the key to successful physical activity for people with disabilities. It involves a gradual increase in

6. PLANNING AND ORGANIZING PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

the intensity, complexity and duration of exercise that is tailored to the individual needs of each person. Starting with simpler and easier exercises, we can gradually move to more complex activities as the person becomes stronger and more capable.

• **Example of a progressive approach:**

- For a person with lower limb mobility impairment: In the first phase, exercises may include light stretching and joint mobility movements. Once the person has gained some flexibility, muscle strengthening exercises for the legs can be added, such as raising the legs from a sitting position.
- For a person with autism: Start with simple coordination activities (e.g. kicking a ball) and gradually add exercises that involve interacting with other members of the group to encourage social and collaborative skills.

The progressiveness is also important in terms of exercise intensity. If a participant feels tired or has difficulty finishing an exercise, we need to adjust the intensity to make it easier, prevent burnout and ensure steady progress.

4. The importance of breaks and recovery

Breaks and recovery periods are essential to prevent injury and maximize the beneficial effects of physical activity. An exercise session should not only be intense, but should also include rest to allow muscles and joints to recover.

• **Examples of breaks and recovery:**

- For a person with severe physical disabilities: Frequent breaks between the sets of exercise, especially if working on parts of the body that are weaker or more fatigued. Breaks can include gentle stretching movements, deep breathing or even muscle relaxation exercises.
- For a person with autism: Breaks can include sensory activities, such as relaxing movements by stimulating the senses (for example, holding a soft object or hearing soothing sounds) to help reduce stress or anxiety levels.
- For a person with mobility impairments: Breaks between active mobility exercises (e.g. between arm rotations or leg raises) are essential to avoid overloading the joints.

The length of the breaks depends on the type and intensity of the exercises, but a general rule of thumb is that the break should be no less than 1-2 minutes for moderate exercises, and for intense workouts, breaks can be longer (3-5 minutes). In addition, stretching and relaxation sessions at the end of the workout help to reduce muscle tension and improve flexibility.

CONCLUSION

Planning and organizing physical activity for people with disabilities should be a careful, personalized activity based on the principle of progressivity. Setting clear goals, creating tailored training sessions, a progressive approach to intensity, and paying special attention to breaks and recovery are fundamental steps to support healthy and effective physical development. Each person has their own pace, and training needs to take this into account to provide a safe and motivating environment.

7. TECHNIQUES AND METHODS FOR ADAPTING EXERCISE

Adaptation of exercise is essential to make activities accessible and effective for people with disabilities, considering the differences in mobility, strength and cognitive abilities. Here are some methods and techniques that can be applied for each type of exercise.

1. Mobility and flexibility exercises

Mobility and flexibility exercises are essential for improving the joint range of motion and preventing muscle stiffness. They are particularly important for people with motor disabilities or mobility limitations as they can help improve their independence and reduce discomfort.

• Examples of mobility and flexibility exercises:

- **For people with motor disabilities (cerebral palsy, amputations, reduced mobility):**
 - **Passive joint movements:** If a person is unable to perform active limb movements, an instructor can help with passive movements (gently pushing or rotating the limbs) to improve joint flexibility. These movements should be slow and controlled to prevent injury.
 - **Arm extension exercises:** People who can move in a chair can raise their arms in a vertical direction, gradually stretching as they raise them. This helps to open the chest and mobilize the shoulders.
- **For the visually impaired people:**
 - **Neck and shoulder stretch:** People with visual impairments can be verbally guided to perform neck and shoulder stretches. For example, verbal guidance may include instructions such as, “Rest your head back and stretch your right arm straight out in front, feeling the stretch in your upper body.”
- **For people with cognitive disabilities (autism, Down syndrome):**
 - **Guided group stretching:** Stretching exercises can be done in a group, with visual and verbal instructions. For example, all participants can raise their arms above their head, slowly pointing them sideways to stretch the chest.

2. Strength and resistance tailored training

Strength training is essential for improving muscles and body stability, while resistance exercises help improve overall fitness.

They should be customized to suit the needs of the individual, especially for those with reduced mobility or muscular impairments.

• Examples of adapted strength and resistance training:

- **For people with partial paralysis:**
 - **Light weight lifting:** A person with limited mobility can do arm strength exercises using small weights (e.g. 1-2 kg) or elastic bands to strengthen the arm muscles. Forward or lateral arm raises and wall push-ups are examples of accessible strength exercises.
 - **Leg press exercises (if there is sufficient mobility):** Raising and lowering one leg in a lying or table-lying position can help strengthen the lower leg muscles.
- **For people with amputations:**
 - **Upper-body strength training:** Lifting weights or using elastic bands for arms and shoulders can help develop upper-body strength. Also for those with lower limb amputations, trunk exercises can help improve stability and posture.
- **For people with intellectual disabilities:**
 - **Simple strength exercises with the help of an instructor:** Using large exercise balls to work on torso stability, such as sitting on the ball and moving your arms at a controlled pace, helps develop muscle strength in an accessible and enjoyable way.

3. Coordination and balance exercises

Coordination and balance are essential for improving stability and preventing falls. Exercises that develop these skills help improve the independence of people with disabilities and contribute to the development of correct posture.

• Examples of adapted exercises for coordination and balance:

- **For people with visual impairments:**
 - **Balance exercises on an imaginary line:** Verbal guidance can help visually impaired people to stand on a straight line and maintain balance for 30 seconds. A challenge can be added, such as lifting one leg and maintaining balance on one leg.
 - **Treadmill walking:** Using constant verbal guidance, walking on the treadmill at a slow speed, focusing on maintaining balance, can be encouraged.
- **For people with coordination impairments (e.g. cerebral palsy):**
 - **Exercises to improve hand-eye coordination:** Throwing a ball to a partner or into a basketball hoop at a lower height helps develop coordination skills.

7. TECHNIQUES AND METHODS FOR ADAPTING EXERCISE

- **Balance exercises on unstable platforms:** people can stand on a balance board or large exercise ball to improve their stability.
- **For people with cognitive impairments:**
 - **Group balance and coordination games:** Games that involve throwing and catching a ball as well as simultaneous movement of arms and legs to develop coordination.

4. Relaxation and breathing exercises

Relaxation and breathing exercises help to reduce stress and anxiety, and integrating them into an exercise session is essential for increasing overall well-being.

• Examples of adapted relaxation and breathing exercises:

- **For people with severe physical disabilities:**
 - **Deep breathing and progressive muscle relaxation:** People can sit in a chair or can remain in a comfortable position, learning to breathe deeply and relax each muscle group, starting from the legs and ending with the head.
 - **Guided relaxation:** Guided relaxation instructions that ask the participant to imagine a soothing place and take deep breaths to help reduce tension and stress.
- **For people with anxiety disorders:**
 - **Controlled breathing techniques:** Training to learn to breathe slowly, with 4-second inhales and 6-second exhales, can help calm the nervous system.
 - **Relaxation through gentle massage or pressure on reflex therapy points:** Applying gentle pressure to specific reflex therapy points can help induce a state of deep relaxation.

5. Using adapted equipment

The use of adapted equipment helps making exercise more accessible and allows people with disabilities to actively participate in various physical activities.

• Examples of adapted equipment:

- **Adapted training chairs:** These are useful for people with limited mobility, who can do strength or cardio exercises without having to stand.
- **Large exercise balls (for balance and strength):** These balls are useful for people with motor or coordination disabili-

ties, helping to improve trunk stability and balance.

- **Elastic bands:** Used to help the development of muscle strength in stretching, mobility and strength exercises. These are suitable for all levels of physical ability.

CONCLUSION

These techniques and methods of exercise adaptations are essential to ensure safe, accessible and effective exercise for people with disabilities. By adjusting exercises and using special equipment, the physical and psychological benefits of physical activity can be maximized, thus contributing to a more active and independent life.

8. COMMUNICATING AND INTERACTING WITH PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

How to create an environment of trust and respect

Creating an environment where people with disabilities feel safe, respected and supported is essential for the start of any physical activity or sport. In addition, this environment favours collaboration, motivation and active participation.

1. Show empathy and patience

It is important to approach people with disabilities with empathy, respecting their pace and giving them enough time to answer questions or understand instructions. Instead of pushing, encourage step-by-step progress without rushing the process.

- **Example:** In a fitness programme for a person with motor disabilities, the instructions should be given calmly and patiently so that the person has time to process each movement or adjustment.

2. Adaptability and flexibility

A coach or instructor must be prepared to adapt the programme or exercises to the needs of each participant. People with disabilities may have different physical and mental responses to the same activities, so flexibility is key. It is important to create an atmosphere where mistakes are encouraged and seen as part of the learning process, not as failures.

- **Example:** If a physical exercise is too hard for a participant, the trainer should offer an easier alternative without making the participant feel uncomfortable or frustrated.

3. Building a trusting relationship

Honest and open communication with people with disabilities is fundamental to building a trusting relationship. It is important for them to know that they can express any concerns or worries, and the trainer needs to be responsive and attentive to their needs.

- **Example:** The trainer could ask the person with a disability what exercises they would like to do or what their limitations are, to ensure that the activity is comfortable and effective.

Communication techniques for people with hearing or speech impairments

People with hearing or speech impairments may require specialized communication techniques to ensure that they understand instructions correctly and can actively participate in sessions.

1. Visual communication

The use of visual cues is essential to help people with hearing impairments to understand instructions more easily. For example, **posters** or **graphic step charts** can detail movements or exercises. Using **illustrations** or **videos** to show the correct technique is also effective.

- **Example:** In a fitness session, the instructor can use a whiteboard to draw or write the steps of the exercise. This will help participants with hearing impairments to follow the activity even if they cannot hear verbal instructions.

2. Sign language

Knowing **sign language** can be essential when working with people with hearing impairments. Even a **basic sign language course** can significantly improve communication and create a closer bond between instructors and participants.

- **Example:** If a hearing-impaired participant does not know full sign language, the instructor can use basic signs (such as ‘push’, ‘pull’, ‘lift’, etc.) to communicate effectively.

3. Using assistive technologies

Technological devices, such as **voice amplification systems, live captioning, or text-to-speech conversation apps**, can facilitate communication with people with speech or hearing impairments. Depending on each person’s needs, their use can reduce communication barriers.

- **Example:** A speech-impaired participant can use a mobile device to enter text and display it on a screen, facilitating the conversation with the instructor.

Strategies for working with people with cognitive disabilities

People with cognitive disabilities may have difficulty understanding complex instructions or abstract concepts. Adapting approaches is essential for successful physical activities.

1. Clear, step-by-step instructions

People with cognitive disabilities benefit from clear, concise and structured instructions. Rather than providing complex information in a single sentence, instructions should be broken down into small, easy-to-understand steps.

- **Example:** In an arm stretching exercise, instructions should be clear and simple, e.g., “Raise straight arm, reach forward, hold for 10 seconds, lower arm.”

2. Repetition and practice

People with cognitive disabilities can learn better by constantly repeating movements and activities. Repetition helps to reinforce learning and increase confidence in skills. Trainers need to be prepared to reiterate instructions several times.

- **Example:** If a participant with **learning disabilities** cannot perform an exercise correctly, the trainer can repeat the exercise several times, providing constant encouragement as the person makes progress.

3. Use visual examples and demonstrations

Demonstrating an exercise in front of the participant can be more effective than giving verbal instructions only. People

8. COMMUNICATING AND INTERACTING WITH PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

with cognitive disabilities often learn more easily by **observation**.

- **Example:** In a balance exercise, the instructor can personally show how to stand in a correct position and then ask the participant to imitate the movement.

The importance of feedback and motivation

Positive and constructive feedback is essential to encourage progress and help people with disabilities to overcome their limitations. It is important that feedback is specific, clear and supportive.

• Positive feedback

Feedback should be mostly **positive** and **motivating**, recognizing progress, even small ones. It is essential that the participant feels that their hard work is appreciated.

- **Example:** “You did a great job lifting this weight! Now let’s try to lift it even higher!”

• Encouraging progress

It is important that feedback focuses on each person’s **individual progress**, not just on reaching the end goals. This helps boost self-esteem and motivation to continue.

- **Example:** If a person with motor disabilities can’t perform a full movement, the instructor can praise progress in the right direction: “That was much better than last time! Keep practicing.”

• Constructive feedback

When there is a need to correct behaviour or techniques, feedback should be constructive and solution-focused. It should also be offered tactfully, without making the participant feel demotivated or offended.

- **Example:** ‘You’ve made great progress, but it would be helpful if you tried to lift your knee more’.

The importance of feedback and motivation (continued)

4. Creating a positive learning environment

An environment in which feedback is consistently positive and supportive helps to build a trusting relationship between the trainer and the learner. Motivation is essential to maintain commitment and to help participants overcome obstacles encountered along the way. Positive feedback is an essential factor in creating an atmosphere in which individual progress is celebrated.

- **Example:** At the end of each session, the trainer can give general feedback on how each participant has progressed, highlighting strengths and improvements made. For example, “Today you did a great job, you made a lot of progress

with your movement co-ordination, and next week we can try to add a more complex exercise.”

5. Set clear and achievable goals

In order to maintain motivation and interest, it is important for each person to have clearly defined goals that are achievable in the short and long term. Goals should be tailored to each person’s needs and abilities and be structured in small, measurable steps. When people achieve these goals, positive feedback helps them to understand that they are on the right track.

- **Example:** If a participant has difficulty running a longer distance, an achievable goal might be to run 100 meters without stopping. Giving positive feedback each time they reach such a goal reinforces the sense of achievement. “You’re getting faster and faster! If you keep this up, you’ll be able to run an even longer distance next time.”

6. Encouraging self-reliance and self-confidence

Feedback should focus not only on correcting technique, but also on developing self-confidence and self-reliance. Encouraging participants to express their own wishes and opinions about exercise can create an atmosphere of empowerment. It can motivate them to become more active and involved in their learning and physical development.

- **Example:** During a workout, the instructor might ask the participant, “How do you feel about this exercise? Do you have any suggestions for how we could improve this?” This type of feedback helps build a more balanced and mutually respectful relationship.

8. COMMUNICATING AND INTERACTING WITH PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

Important considerations for personalizing the communication

In order to ensure effective communication and interaction, it is essential that each person with a disability is treated on an individualized basis, considering their specific characteristics and needs. Here are some key reflections:

1. Self-reflection and continuous evaluation of communication strategies

Trainers need to be flexible and to constantly adapt their communication approaches according to the participants' responses and developments. Continuous evaluation of progress and adjustment of feedback are essential for the success of physical activities.

- **Example:** After each session, the trainer could reflect on his/her communication and note which of the techniques used were most effective. If participants with cognitive disabilities had difficulties, the instructor could try other methods, such as using icons or interactive games.

2. The relationship between non-verbal language and effective communication

In many cases, non-verbal language (gestures, mimicry, facial expressions) plays a crucial role in communicating with people with disabilities, especially when there is a verbal communication barrier. In this context, the use of overt and encouraging body language can supplement or reinforce verbal messages.

- **Example:** When giving instructions, instructors can use clear gestures, mimics and facial expressions to emphasize certain actions, such as smiling and affirmative gestures to support understanding.

CONCLUSION: Communication is the key to success

Effective communication with people with disabilities is one of the most important tools in creating a learning and physical development environment. By adopting clear language, creating a climate of trust and respect, and applying motivational feedback techniques tailored to each type of disability, coaches and disability professionals can facilitate the physical and psychological progress and well-being of participants.

Tips to improve communication:

- Pay attention to people's non-verbal reactions and adapt your style according to their feedback.
 - Make sure any instructions or messages are repeated, clarified and checked for understanding.
 - Always give feedback that not only corrects but encourages so that every progress, however small, is appreciated.
 - Be flexible and adapt communication techniques according to each person's needs and abilities.
- So, through an integrative approach, tailored to the individual needs of each participant, we can contribute to a learning and development environment where people with disabilities feel not only included, but also encouraged to reach their full potential.

9. SAFETY AND ACCIDENT PREVENTION

In physical activities for people with disabilities, safety is essential. Any sports programme must consider the specific risks of each disability and implement measures to prevent accidents and injuries. This includes precautions, risk identification and rapid intervention in case of emergency.

Precautions and safety in physical activity

1. Prior assessment of the participant's health

Before beginning any physical activity programme, it is important for the instructor to obtain information about the participant's health, including medical history, type of disability and any other conditions that might influence exercise safety. This may include:

- Consultation with a health professional.

- Obtaining a consent form from the person's doctor or family for physical activity.
- Setting clear and realistic limits on the type and intensity of exercise.
 - **Example:** If a participant has a cardiovascular condition, the instructor should ensure that the intensity of exercise is adapted to the participant's capabilities, avoiding over-exertion.

2. Providing a safe practice environment

It is essential that the place where physical activities take place to be well maintained and safe. This means:

- Smooth and obstacle-free surfaces.
- Use of appropriate equipment, such as comfortable sports footwear and appropriate protective gear.
- Ensuring that the equipment used (balls, ropes, weights) is in good working order and is adapted for people with disabilities (e.g. adjustable weights for people with reduced mobility).
 - **Example:** When working with people with mobility impairments, instructors should ensure that the exercise spaces are wheelchair accessible and there are no steps or obstacles that could cause falls.

3. Proper warm-up and cool-down

A proper warm-up and cool-down at the end of the session is essential to prevent injury and protect joints and muscles. This can include stretching exercises and joint mobilizing activities.

- **Example:** Before starting any intense exercise, it is recommended that participants carry out an active warm-up (light joint mobilizing exercises) and at the end do stretching exercises to prevent muscle cramps or injuries.

Identifying specific risks by type of disability

Each type of disability may present different risks during physical activities. Depending on this, instructors should identify and adapt exercises accordingly to prevent injuries.

1. People with motor disabilities

Risks for people with motor disabilities may include:

- **Falls due to reduced mobility** - people with reduced mobility need to be helped to maintain their balance during exercises.
- **Muscle strain** - mobilizing joints may cause discomfort or pain, especially if repetitive movements are involved.**re-cautions:**
 - The use of support equipment such as wheelchairs or assistive devices.
 - Balance exercises that are carried out step-by-step and closely monitored.

9. SAFETY AND ACCIDENT PREVENTION

- Providing an instructor to assist the participant during difficult movements.

2. People with sensory disabilities (hearing or vision impairments)

People with hearing or sight impairments may have difficulty perceiving warning signals or verbal instructions. These risks may include:

- **Accidents due to lack of perception of environmental cues** - for example, the lack of an audible signal may prevent an exercise from starting correctly or may lead to failure to notice alarm signals (for example, a sound indicating a problem with equipment).

Precautions:

- Use visual or other types of signals to indicate the start of an exercise or changes of pace.
- Create detailed instructions that are presented in an accessible form, either in writing or through visual signals.

3. People with cognitive disabilities

For people with cognitive disabilities, the risks are related to:

- Difficulty in understanding instructions - the risk of performing an exercise incorrectly due to incomplete understanding of the exercise.
- Not being aware of their own limits - they may overload the body as they may not understand signs of fatigue or pain.

Precautions:

- Giving short, clear instructions, using repetition to help the participant understand exactly what to do.
- Carefully monitor the participant's level of fatigue and adjust exercises to prevent overexertion.

First aid and emergency measures

Regardless of the type of disability, accidents can occur during physical activities. Therefore, it is essential that all instructors are trained to intervene quickly in the event of an emergency.

1. First aid training

Every instructor should be trained in first aid, including first aid measures in the event of an accident or injury. These may include:

- **Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR)** in the event of cardiopulmonary arrest.
- **Application of a bandage or dressing** in the event of cuts or sprains.

Example: In the event of a fall, the instructor should know how to apply a compression bandage to reduce bleeding and continuously monitor the victim's vital signs.

2. Emergency equipment

In every physical activity venue, there should be emergency equipment available, including first aid kits, automated external defibrillators (AEDs) and telephones to quickly contact emergency services.

- **Example:** If a person with a disability has a severe allergic reaction to a particular material or product, there should be an emergency kit that includes injectable adrenaline and the instructor should be trained how to administer it. **Plan an emergency protocol**

Every sports facility should have a clear emergency protocol that includes exact steps on how to respond to accidents and ensure that medical help is sought immediately.

- **Example:** In the case of a person with epilepsy, the instructor needs to know exactly what steps to take in the event of a seizure, such as protecting the victim's head and keeping the airway open.

CONCLUSION: Safety as a priority

Safety and accident prevention are fundamental elements in physical activity for people with disabilities. By identifying specific risks and implementing tailored safety measures, instructors can create a safe and effective training environment, ensuring that all participants benefit from a positive, hazard-free experience.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Adapted physical and sports activities are essential for people with disabilities as they enable them to actively participate in exercise and enjoy the benefits of sport, such as improved physical, mental and social health. These activities are personalized according to the type of disability, individual needs and abilities of each person. We will explore some examples of physical and sporting activities that can be adapted, giving practical examples for each.

1. Team sports (football, adapted basketball)

Team sports can be an excellent opportunity to encourage collaboration, team spirit and the development of social skills.

They can be adapted to meet the needs of people with various disabilities.

Example of activities:

- **Adapted football:** In adapted football, larger or softer balls can be used and the size of the pitch can be reduced to allow better accessibility. People with reduced mobility can play wheelchair football, actively participating in the game by passing and dribbling. In wheelchair football, there are rules that limit physical contact, and teams are formed so that all participants can integrate effectively into the game.
- **Wheelchair basketball:** Wheelchair basketball is an adapted version in which athletes play on specially adapted courts using wheelchairs. The games are played according to similar rules to traditional basketball, but with some modifications, such as the length of the game and the number of steps allowed. These modifications allow people with amputations, paralysis or motor disabilities to participate.

Complementary Benefits for Team Sports

- **Enhanced collaboration and team spirit:** Team sports, including adapted versions, encourage cooperation, mutual support, and effective communication, fostering a sense of camaraderie and belonging.
- **Social skills development:** Participating in team sports promotes the development of social interaction, empathy, and teamwork, helping individuals build stronger interpersonal relationships and confidence in group settings.

- **Physical fitness and motor skills improvement:** Adapted sports like wheelchair basketball and football help improve coordination, strength, endurance, and mobility, contributing to overall physical health and fitness.
- **Inclusion and empowerment:** By adapting team sports to accommodate various disabilities, participants are empowered to actively engage in competitive and recreational activities, enhancing their self-esteem and sense of achievement.
- **Emotional well-being and stress relief:** Team sports offer a healthy outlet for emotional expression and stress management, helping participants regulate emotions and feel a sense of accomplishment.
- **Disability awareness and breaking barriers:** Engaging in mixed-ability team sports promotes understanding and awareness of disability-related challenges, helping break down social barriers and build more inclusive communities.
- **Rehabilitation and functional independence:** Wheelchair basketball and adapted football, among other team sports, assist in rehabilitation by improving physical function, mobility, and independence, helping individuals regain or maintain physical abilities.

2. Swimming and water activities

Swimming is a particularly beneficial activity for people with disabilities as the water reduces the impact on joints and provides greater freedom of movement. Water activities can be very varied and can be adapted according to the type of disability.

Example of activities:

- **Swimming for people with reduced mobility:** People with motor disabilities can participate in aquatic activities, such as swimming, with the help of assistive devices such as trust rafts or special water frames. Swimming exercises such as backstroke or arm strokes can help improve mobility and muscle strength.
- **Relaxation exercises in the water:** Breathing, stretching and relaxation exercises can also be implemented as part of water activities. Individuals with severe physical disabilities can perform light movements in the water, such as stretching their arms and legs, or do mobility exercises to help increase flexibility.
- **Move and coordination exercises in the water:** Some swimming activities may include games that help participants coordinate their arm and leg movements in the water, encouraging the development of balance and coordination skills.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Complementary Benefits for Swimming and Water Activities

- **Low-impact exercise:** Water provides buoyancy, reducing stress on joints and minimizing the risk of injury, making swimming and water activities ideal for individuals with mobility impairments or chronic conditions.
- **Enhanced muscle strength and mobility:** Swimming and water exercises, such as arm strokes or leg movements, help improve muscle strength, flexibility, and range of motion, supporting greater mobility and overall physical fitness.
- **Improved coordination and balance:** Water activities, especially games or exercises involving coordination of arms and legs, promote balance and motor control, which can be particularly beneficial for individuals with motor disabilities.
- **Mental relaxation and stress relief:** Water's calming effect, combined with relaxation exercises like stretching and breathing, helps reduce stress and anxiety, promoting mental relaxation and emotional well-being.
- **Increased independence and confidence:** The freedom of movement in the water can enhance participants' sense of autonomy and confidence as they gain control over their movements and physical abilities.
- **Support for rehabilitation and recovery:** Water activities can be an excellent rehabilitation tool, aiding in recovery from physical injuries by providing a gentle, therapeutic environment for exercise and stretching.
- **Social engagement:** Group water sessions encourage socialization and interaction among participants, helping to break down barriers and foster a sense of community.

3. Adapted yoga and gymnastics

Gymnastics and yoga are excellent activities for developing flexibility, balance, strength and relaxation. Both gymnastics and yoga can be adapted for people with disabilities, helping to improve posture, breathing and concentration.

- **Example of activities:**
 - **Adapted Yoga:** Yoga can be practiced by people with reduced mobility as well as those with normal physical abilities. For people with mobility or balance impairments, special chairs can be used to facilitate movements. Exercises can include stretching of arms and legs, improving breathing and relaxing the body. For example, 'child's pose' (Balasana) can be modified so that it can be performed in a chair, while breathing techniques can be guided to help reduce stress and anxiety.
 - **Adapted gymnastics for people with motor disabilities:** Gymnastic exercises can be adapted by using additional supports or by modifying the intensity of the movements. For example, for people with lower limb amputations, the

toning exercises for leg stretching can be performed with the use of devices or bandages. Simple movements such as stretching the arms can help improve flexibility and mobility.

Complementary Benefits for Adapted Yoga and Gymnastics

- **Improved physical health:** Both adapted yoga and gymnastics help enhance flexibility, balance, strength, and coordination, contributing to better posture, mobility, and overall physical fitness.
- **Mental relaxation and stress relief:** Yoga, in particular, promotes deep breathing and mindfulness, which help reduce anxiety, stress, and tension. This leads to improved emotional well-being and relaxation.
- **Increased focus and concentration:** Yoga's emphasis on controlled breathing and mindful movements can enhance focus and concentration, making it beneficial for individuals with cognitive challenges as well.
- **Boosted confidence and independence:** Adapted exercises foster a sense of accomplishment and autonomy, helping individuals gain confidence in their abilities and build self-esteem.
- **Enhanced body awareness:** Both disciplines promote better proprioception (awareness of body position), which can be particularly helpful for individuals with motor disabilities to improve coordination and control.
- **Support for mental health:** By promoting relaxation, physical movement, and mindfulness, adapted yoga and gymnastics help improve mental clarity, emotional regulation, and overall mental health.
- **Social inclusion:** Group sessions foster interaction and communication between participants, helping to build social skills and reduce isolation among individuals with disabilities.

4. Outdoor activities (hiking, cycling)

Outdoor activities are excellent for improving general health and are good for both body and mind. They can be adapted to meet the needs of people with disabilities and can be an excellent opportunity for socializing.

- **Example of activities:**
 - **Hiking for people with motor disabilities:** Hiking can be adapted by using specially designed field chairs for use on mountain trails or rough paths. These chairs are equipped with large wheels that allow a person with reduced mobility to actively participate in a hike. Group hikes can also encourage integration and provide mental and emotional support.
 - **Adapted cycling:** People with disabilities can participate in cycling using specialized bicycles, such as wheelchair bikes or three-wheeled bicycles. These bikes are designed to ensure stability and safety, and cycling routes can be easily modified according to the level of difficulty of the participants.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Complementary Benefits for Outdoor Activities (Hiking, Cycling)

- **Physical health improvement:** Outdoor activities promote cardiovascular health, muscle strength, flexibility, and endurance, all of which are crucial for overall well-being.
- **Mental well-being:** Nature-based activities, like hiking and cycling, have been shown to reduce stress, anxiety, and depression while enhancing mood and promoting a positive outlook.
- **Social interaction and inclusion:** Group outdoor activities provide an excellent platform for socializing, reducing isolation, and building supportive communities, especially for people with disabilities.
- **Increased independence:** Adapted outdoor activities foster a sense of autonomy, allowing participants to engage in nature and outdoor exploration in a manner suited to their abilities.
- **Enhanced self-esteem and confidence:** Successfully participating in hiking or cycling helps boost self-esteem and encourages a sense of achievement, which fosters personal growth.
- **Cognitive stimulation:** Navigating outdoor environments and adjusting to varying terrains improve spatial awareness, focus, and problem-solving skills.
- **Connection with nature:** Engaging with natural environments has therapeutic effects, offering relaxation and a sense of peace, which contributes to emotional balance.

5. Dance and movement techniques

Dance is a very versatile activity that can be adapted for people with various disabilities. Rhythmic movements and choreography help develop coordination, balance and flexibility.

- **Example of activities:**
 - **Adapted dances:** people with mobility disabilities can dance in wheelchairs or dance standing with the help of partners. The dance can include arm movements and twisting, accompanied by musical rhythms. For example, one type of adapted dance is Wheelchair Dance Sport, where partners can dance in wheelchairs, following a common rhythm.
 - **Therapeutic dance:** Therapeutic dance can be used to help participants express their emotions and improve body awareness. The rhythmic movements help coordination, flexibility and reduce tension.

Complementary Benefits for Dance and Movement Techniques

- **Improved mobility and coordination:** Dance helps enhance balance, flexibility, and motor control, especially for individuals

with mobility challenges.

- **Emotional expression:** Dance serves as an effective outlet for expressing emotions, improving mental well-being and offering a sense of release and relaxation.
- **Social inclusion:** Group dance activities foster teamwork, social interaction, and collaboration, promoting a sense of belonging and reducing isolation.
- **Increased confidence:** Successfully performing dance routines boosts self-esteem and empowers participants, helping them feel proud of their physical and emotional progress.
- **Cognitive and sensory stimulation:** Dance enhances cognitive functions such as concentration, memory, and focus while also engaging sensory awareness through music and movement.
- **Therapeutic benefits:** Dance serves as a form of physical therapy, aiding in the reduction of stress and tension while promoting relaxation and overall well-being.
- **Creative expression:** Dance encourages creativity, providing participants with the opportunity to explore self-expression and individuality through movement.

6. Competitive sports for people with disabilities

Adapted competitive sports offer excellent opportunities for performance and self-improvement for people with disabilities. They are regulated by international organizations and can include a variety of disciplines.

- **Example of activities:**
 - **Paralympics:** This is a significant example of elite competition for people with disabilities. Sports such as swimming, athletics, table tennis, wheelchair basketball or volleyball are available for participants. These sports are regulated by the International Paralympic Federation and are adapted to allow participation by people with different types of disabilities.
 - **Adapted cycling competitions:** There are international cycling competitions for people with disabilities that use special bicycles, including three-wheeled bicycles or wheelchair bicycles. These competitions are an excellent opportunity to encourage participation and sports performance.

Complementary Benefits for Competitive Sports for People with Disabilities

- **Enhanced physical fitness:** Adapted competitive sports improve overall physical health, strength, and endurance, helping individuals achieve their personal bests.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

- **Social inclusion:** These sports provide a platform for athletes to interact with peers, fostering teamwork, communication, and a sense of community.
- **Self-esteem and empowerment:** Success in competitive events boosts confidence and self-worth, promoting a positive self-image among athletes.
- **Mental resilience:** Training and competition help athletes develop mental toughness, discipline, and the ability to cope with challenges and setbacks.
- **Opportunities for personal growth:** Participation in high-level competition encourages continuous improvement, pushing athletes to set and achieve new goals.
- **Equality and recognition:** Competitive sports ensure that individuals with disabilities have equal opportunities to showcase their talents and compete on an international stage.

Global connection: International competitions, like the Paralympics, provide a sense of belonging to a global network of athletes with disabilities, promoting a shared sense of pride and achievement.

7. Goalball

Goalball is a unique team sport designed specifically for individuals with visual impairments or blindness. It emphasizes sensory skills, spatial awareness, and teamwork, offering an inclusive and competitive environment. Players rely on auditory cues to follow the game and navigate the court using their sense of touch.

• Example of activities:

- **Competitive gameplay:** Goalball is played by two teams of three players on an indoor court. The objective is to score by rolling a ball with bells inside into the opposing team's goal. Players block the ball using their bodies, relying on sound to track it.
- **Paralympic participation:** Goalball is an official sport in the Paralympic Games, highlighting the athleticism and skills of visually impaired athletes. All players wear eyeshades to ensure equality, regardless of the level of impairment.
- **Training sessions:** Goalball training emphasizes techniques such as controlled throws, defensive positioning, and team coordination. Communication is essential, and training often includes drills to enhance auditory focus and spatial orientation.
- **Sensory skill development:** This sport is highly effective in improving listening skills, reaction time, and proprioception. It also helps boost confidence and promotes physical fitness among participants.

Complementary Benefits for Goalball

- **Improved sensory skills:** Goalball enhances auditory focus and spatial awareness, as players track the ball through sound, strengthening listening skills and proprioception.
- **Physical fitness:** The sport boosts cardiovascular health, strength, and agility through quick reflexes and intense movement.
- **Teamwork and social inclusion:** Encourages cooperation and communication, fostering a sense of community and belonging among players.
- **Better communication:** Goalball strengthens verbal expression and listening skills through constant team interaction and strategy discussions.
- **Confidence and independence:** Participation builds self-esteem and encourages personal responsibility, enhancing confidence both on and off the court.
- **Emotional resilience:** The sport helps athletes develop mental toughness, learning to manage setbacks and pressure during competition.
- **Sense of achievement:** Provides athletes with a sense of accomplishment and equality, creating an inclusive environment where everyone can compete based on skill.

8. Para Judo

Parajudo is an adapted martial art based on traditional judo, tailored for athletes with visual impairments. It maintains the core principles of judo—such as balance, discipline, and technique—while ensuring fairness through rule adjustments and classification systems.

• Example of activities:

- **Adapted matches:** In para judo, matches start with both athletes in a grip position (kumikata), ensuring immediate contact. If the grip is lost, the referee pauses the match and resets it. This adaptation maintains flow and safety.
- **Paralympic competition:** Para judo has been part of the Paralympic Games since 1988 (for men) and 2004 (for women). Athletes are classified into J1 (blind) and J2 (partially sighted) to ensure balanced competition.
- **Tactile training and techniques:** Training focuses on tactile sensitivity, balance, and spatial awareness. Athletes practice throws and holds adapted to their sensory perception, with an emphasis on maintaining the essence of judo technique.
- **Physical and emotional development:** Para judo enhances strength, flexibility, and confidence. It also fosters discipline, respect, and camaraderie—essential values in martial arts and in adaptive sports in general.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Complementary Benefits for Para Judo

- **Improved physical fitness and coordination:** Para judo provides a comprehensive physical workout that develops strength, flexibility, and overall body coordination. The training enhances balance and spatial awareness, both of which are crucial in martial arts, while also improving muscular endurance through techniques such as throws and holds.
- **Enhanced tactile sensitivity and spatial awareness:** Since para judo athletes rely on tactile sensations rather than visual cues, it significantly enhances their ability to sense and react to touch, body positioning, and opponent movement. This increased tactile awareness contributes to better performance in martial arts and in daily life.
- **Self-discipline and focus:** Just like traditional judo, para judo emphasizes mental discipline and focus. Athletes develop a deep understanding of the importance of concentration, respect for opponents, and maintaining control under pressure. These qualities extend beyond the mat, contributing to better emotional regulation and resilience in everyday challenges.
- **Empowerment and self-esteem:** Competing in para judo allows athletes to gain a sense of empowerment by demonstrating their physical and mental strength. Achieving success in the sport boosts self-confidence and fosters a positive self-image, proving that athletes can excel despite their visual impairments.
- **Social integration and camaraderie:** Para judo creates a supportive community where athletes with visual impairments form strong connections with their peers. The teamwork and mutual respect required in judo competitions foster a sense of camaraderie, social inclusion, and belonging, combating feelings of isolation.
- **Emotional growth and resilience:** Para judo promotes emotional well-being by teaching athletes to persevere through challenges, both on and off the mat. Athletes learn how to manage setbacks, celebrate achievements, and develop resilience, cultivating a sense of emotional strength that positively influences their overall mental health.
- **Sense of achievement and purpose:** The structured nature of para judo, with its clear objectives in training and competition, provides athletes with measurable goals and a sense of purpose. Achievements in training or competition give athletes a strong sense of accomplishment, which can have a positive impact on their motivation and personal development.

9. Sitting volleyball

Adapted volleyball is a dynamic and inclusive sport that allows individuals with physical disabilities to actively en-

gage in team-based competition. It emphasizes agility, coordination, and communication, offering both recreational and competitive opportunities. One of the most popular forms is sitting volleyball, a Paralympic sport played by athletes with lower limb impairments..

• Example of activities:

- **Sitting volleyball:** Played on a smaller court with a lower net, sitting volleyball requires players to remain seated on the floor while playing. It emphasizes quick reflexes, strong upper body movement, and teamwork. This sport is included in the Paralympic Games and follows modified rules to ensure fair and exciting gameplay.
- **Recreational adapted volleyball:** In community or rehabilitation settings, volleyball can be adapted further with flexible rules, lighter balls, or the use of assistive devices. This promotes inclusion and encourages physical activity for individuals with various mobility challenges.
- **Training and skill development:** Athletes train to improve their serving, blocking, passing, and strategic positioning—all while seated. Team coordination and communication are essential, making this a sport that also fosters social interaction and mutual support.
- **Inclusive tournaments and leagues:** Adapted volleyball is practiced at both amateur and professional levels, with local, national, and international competitions providing visibility and recognition for athletes with disabilities.

Complementary Benefits for Sitting volleyball

- **Enhanced physical fitness:** Sitting volleyball provides an excellent full-body workout, focusing on upper body strength, coordination, and agility. Athletes work on their core stability and arm strength, while also improving reflexes and spatial awareness, contributing to overall physical health.
- **Social inclusion and team cohesion:** As a team sport, sitting volleyball fosters strong bonds among players, promoting a sense of community and belonging. The emphasis on communication, trust, and cooperation builds team spirit and creates an inclusive environment where athletes with disabilities can interact with their peers and feel valued.
- **Increased mobility and functional independence:** Sitting volleyball promotes the development of upper body and core strength, which can improve functional mobility and independence. Players can enhance their ability to move, pivot, and respond quickly while seated, contributing to greater overall physical function.
- **Emotional well-being and self-esteem:** The team dynamic and sense of accomplishment from competitive play help boost self-esteem and emotional well-being. By participating in competitive and recreational games, players experience a sense of achievement, which enhances personal confidence and fosters a positive self-image.
- **Therapeutic benefits and rehabilitation:** Sitting volleyball can be an excellent therapeutic activity for individuals

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

with lower limb impairments or those undergoing rehabilitation. The sport helps improve muscle tone, flexibility, and endurance while providing a structured and enjoyable activity that can be adapted to suit the needs of each individual.

• **Promotion of perseverance and resilience:** The adaptive nature of sitting volleyball challenges players to push beyond their physical limitations, building resilience and perseverance. The focus on skill development, teamwork, and overcoming challenges fosters a mindset of determination and the ability to thrive despite adversity.

10. Inclusive Cue Sports

Inclusive cue sports offer accessible and engaging opportunities for individuals with physical, sensory, or cognitive disabilities. Through adapted rules and equipment, billiards and similar activities are transformed into powerful educational and social tools.

• Example of activities:

- **Modified equipment sessions:** Players use customized cues, larger or lighter balls, and height-adjustable tables to accommodate different needs. These tools allow participants to develop coordination, concentration, and confidence in a supportive environment.
- **Group instruction and peer support:** Sessions are held in small groups with the guidance of trained instructors and inclusion professionals. Peer collaboration is encouraged, fostering social interaction and mutual learning.
- **Integrated play:** Inclusive cue sports often include mixed sessions involving individuals with and without disabilities. These activities promote empathy, cooperation, and equality in sporting environments.
- **Educational and therapeutic focus:** The methodology emphasizes individual feedback, socialization, and personal development, aligning with principles of sport for all. Billiards becomes a vehicle for emotional regulation, self-esteem building, and relational growth.

Complementary Benefits for Inclusive Cue Sports

- **Enhanced physical and cognitive skills:** Inclusive cue sports help individuals develop fine motor skills, hand-eye coordination, and concentration. By adapting equipment and rules, players with various physical, sensory, or cognitive challenges can engage in sports that stimulate both physical and mental abilities, offering a full-body workout while enhancing focus and strategy.
- **Social integration and empathy building:** Through mixed play sessions involving individuals with and without disabilities, inclusive cue sports break down barriers, promote inclusivity, and foster empathy. Social interaction and peer support are central, encouraging the development of friendships and mutual respect in a diverse community.

• **Boosted confidence and self-esteem:** By emphasizing individual progress over competition, inclusive cue sports build players' self-confidence and self-worth. Participants gain a sense of accomplishment and pride in their abilities, boosting their emotional well-being and encouraging a positive outlook.

• **Emotional regulation and personal development:** The structured nature of inclusive cue sports provides participants with an opportunity to practice emotional regulation, particularly through the mindfulness required during gameplay. These sessions help individuals manage their emotions, develop patience, and build resilience in a supportive and non-judgmental setting.

• **Therapeutic benefits and life skills:** Inclusive cue sports offer therapeutic value by providing a structured yet enjoyable activity. Participants can develop social skills, teamwork, and leadership abilities through group activities, while gaining therapeutic benefits related to balance, mobility, and motor control.

11. Inclusive Skating

Inclusive skating makes skating accessible to individuals with physical, intellectual, or relational disabilities. The educational approach is inclusive and progressive, taking into account different skill levels and learning paces. Through person-centered instructions, it promotes autonomy, participation, and celebration of progress.

• Example of activities:

- **Integrated training sessions:** Skating lessons are organized into adaptable modules based on participants' abilities. Exercises focus on balance, rhythm, and coordination, while also supporting relational and social development.
- **Assistive tools and support:** Instructors use visually marked paths, stability aids, and inclusive teaching strategies to create a safe and engaging experience.
- **The final tournament:** An annual friendly event celebrates each skater's journey, focusing on participation rather than competition. Symbolic awards, music, and games highlight effort and personal growth.
- **Collaborative environment:** Inclusive skating promotes interaction between athletes of different abilities, helping to break down social barriers and build respect and friendship.

Complementary Benefits for Inclusive Skating

- **Psychomotor Development:** Inclusive skating promotes psychomotor well-being by engaging participants in activities that develop balance, coordination, body awareness, and self-confidence, supporting both physical and emotional growth.
- **Inclusive Environments:** the design of the course offers safe and inclusive sporting environments where every individual feels welcomed, valued, and supported—spaces that celebrate difference rather than judge it.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

- **Peer Connection and Respect:** peer relationships are encouraged through sports dynamics that foster mutual respect, cooperation, and team spirit—on and off the playing field or rink.
- **Recognition Through Events:** events such as friendly tournaments, open sessions, and community showcases provide opportunities for public recognition of the educational and social value of inclusive sport and athletes.
- **Community and Network Building:** Inclusive skating strengthens local networks by building active collaborations between families, schools, community associations, and professionals to promote a culture of inclusion and active citizenship.

12. Inclusive Football

Inclusive football serves as a rehabilitation and social inclusion tool for individuals facing psychological distress. In a supportive team setting, football promotes well-being, empowerment, and community connection.

• Example of activities:

- **Therapeutic training sessions:** Led by trained educators and mental health professionals, football sessions focus on motor skills, group dynamics, and emotional expression.
- **Adapted gameplay:** Teams are mixed in age, skill, and gender, and rules are modified based on group needs. Emphasis is placed on participation and enjoyment rather than competition.
- **Trust-building activities:** Sessions include exercises that strengthen communication and cooperation, fostering a sense of belonging and mutual support.
- **Beyond the pitch:** Extra-sport activities such as shared meals, music, or social gatherings help strengthen group cohesion and reduce isolation.
- **Empowerment through roles:** Players are encouraged to take on responsibilities within the team, such as captain, assistant, or peer mentor, supporting autonomy and self-worth.

Complementary Benefits for Inclusive Football

- **Mental health support and emotional expression:** Inclusive football offers a safe and supportive environment where individuals can express their emotions and work through psychological challenges, fostering better mental well-being and reducing feelings of isolation.
- **Social inclusion and community connection:** The team-based nature of the sport helps create strong bonds among players, promoting a sense of belonging and reducing social isolation, particularly for individuals dealing with mental health struggles or psychological distress.
- **Enhanced physical health and motor skills:** Football exercises improve coordination, balance, and fitness, which are beneficial for both physical rehabilitation and overall well-being. Adapted training ensures that everyone can participate at their own level.

- **Development of life skills:** Football fosters skills like teamwork, communication, and leadership. By taking on roles such as team captain or mentor, players gain confidence, a sense of responsibility, and autonomy, all of which contribute to personal growth.
- **Positive social interactions and empowerment:** The inclusive environment encourages mixed-age, skill, and gender teams, which helps break down barriers, fosters mutual respect, and empowers participants to connect and collaborate with others in a supportive atmosphere.

13. Adapted Swimming and Aquatic Exercise (AFA, AMA)

Adapted aquatic activities ensure continuous access to movement-based wellness for individuals with disabilities or chronic conditions. These programs foster autonomy, inclusion, and physical health in safe, accessible environments.

• Example of activities:

- **AFA (Adapted Physical Activity):** Low-impact water exercises aimed at improving strength, flexibility, and overall wellness in elderly individuals or those with chronic conditions.
- **AMA (Adapted Motor Activity):** Targeted exercises for individuals with neurological or intellectual disabilities, promoting motor function and independence.
- **Adapted swimming:** Techniques focused on floating, controlled breathing, and aquatic movement to boost confidence and water safety.
- **Aquatic exercise:** Gentle, therapeutic workouts in water for improved mobility and relaxation, especially suited to individuals with musculoskeletal issues.
- **Multidisciplinary support:** Sessions are supervised by instructors and health professionals, with full physical and sensory accessibility in all facilities.

Complementary Benefits for Adapted Swimming and Aquatic Exercise (AFA, AMA)

- **Improved physical health and mobility:** Water-based activities provide a low-impact environment that reduces stress on joints while enhancing cardiovascular health, muscle tone, and flexibility—ideal for individuals with chronic pain, arthritis, or reduced mobility.
- **Enhanced motor skills and functional independence:** Targeted aquatic programs (especially under AMA) support the development of gross and fine motor skills, helping individuals with neurological or intellectual disabilities increase autonomy in daily activities.
- **Boosted emotional well-being and relaxation:** The calming effect of water, combined with rhythmic movement and gentle resistance, helps reduce anxiety, improve mood, and promote mental clarity.

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

- **Increased confidence and water safety:** Adapted swimming techniques foster a sense of security, accomplishment, and familiarity with water, contributing to long-term safety and self-assurance in aquatic environments.
- **Inclusive and therapeutic environment:** The sensory-friendly setting, multidisciplinary supervision, and accessible facilities ensure that participants of all ages and abilities can engage in meaningful physical activity at their own pace.

14. Adapted Thai Boxing

Adapted Thai boxing makes Muay Thai accessible to individuals with cognitive, emotional, or behavioral challenges. This inclusive martial art supports emotional regulation, concentration, and social connection in a non-competitive setting.

- **Example of activities:**
 - **Structured sessions:** Classes follow a predictable format (greetings, basic techniques, partner work) that supports attention and emotional regulation through routine.
 - **Adapted martial techniques:** Traditional Muay Thai movements are simplified and ritualized to meet individual needs, allowing participants to channel energy constructively.
 - **Emotional and sensory development:** Breathing techniques, rhythmic movements, and controlled contact help manage frustration and develop body awareness.
 - **Cooperative learning:** Pair exercises and group activities build trust, empathy, and communication among participants.
 - **Inclusive teaching tools:** Visual aids, sound cues, and consistent routines reduce anxiety and improve learning, supporting personal growth over performance outcomes.
- **Complementary Benefits for Adapted Thai Boxing**
 - **Emotional self-regulation:** The repetitive and ritualized nature of Muay Thai techniques helps participants manage stress, frustration, and impulsive behavior, promoting calmness and emotional control.
 - **Improved concentration and routine adherence:** Structured class formats and consistent routines foster attention span, mental focus, and a sense of predictability—particularly beneficial for individuals with ADHD, autism spectrum disorders, or anxiety.
 - **Enhanced body awareness and sensory integration:** Through controlled physical contact, rhythmic movement, and breathing exercises, participants gain better control of their bodies and improve sensory processing abilities.
 - **Social and emotional connection:** Partner and group exercises encourage teamwork, trust-building, empathy, and verbal/non-verbal communication—key components of emotional intelligence and social inclusion.
 - **Inclusive and non-competitive setting:** With an emphasis on personal growth over competition, Adapted Thai Boxing provides a safe and empowering environment for individuals who may otherwise feel excluded from traditional sports.

15. Boccia (Indoor Bowls for Persons with Physical Disabilities)

Boccia is a Paralympic precision sport designed for individuals with severe physical disabilities, particularly those who use wheelchairs. It is a highly strategic and inclusive activity, where success depends more on skill and concentration than physical strength. The game promotes social inclusion and engagement in a safe, controlled environment, allowing players to develop focus, coordination, and teamwork through sport.

- **Example of activities:**
 - **Game structure:** Each player or team uses six balls (red or blue) to get as close as possible to a white target ball (the jack). The game is played indoors on a 6m x 12.5m court, either individually, in pairs, or in teams.
 - **Methods of play:** Balls can be thrown with the hand, foot, or with the assistance of a ramp, depending on the athlete's ability.
 - **Functional classification:** Players are grouped into four sport classes (BC1-BC4), based on their mobility level and diagnosis (e.g., cerebral palsy, muscular dystrophy, paraplegia).
 - **Technical adaptations:** Athletes may use assistive devices (like head pointers or sport assistants), with rules adjusted to maximize inclusion and participation.
 - **Competition and integration:** Boccia is an official Paralympic sport and is featured in every edition of the Paralympic Games. It is also practiced at local, national, and international levels within adapted sports federations.
- **Complementary Benefits for Boccia (Indoor Bowls for Persons with Physical Disabilities)**
 - **Social inclusion:** Boccia fosters interaction and communication between players, coaches, and families, promoting a sense of belonging and personal value.
 - **Cognitive and motor development:** Strategic planning, spatial awareness, and motor control are naturally developed through gameplay.
 - **High accessibility:** The sport requires minimal resources and is easy to learn, making it suitable for all ages and levels of ability.

16. Para-Alpine Skiing

Para-alpine skiing is a high-performance winter sport designed to include athletes with a wide range of physical and visual impairments. Known for its speed, precision, and technical difficulty, para-alpine skiing mirrors the structure and challenges of mainstream alpine skiing. Athletes compete on the same courses used in elite-level international events, under the regulations of the International Ski Federation (FIS). The sport offers equitable participation through detailed classification sy-

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

stems and specialized equipment, allowing individuals with disabilities to perform at the highest competitive level.

• Example of activities:

- **Competition categories:** Athletes compete in three main categories based on functional ability:
 - ✓ Visually impaired skiers, who race with a sighted guide using verbal instructions.
 - ✓ Standing skiers, who may use orthotic supports, prosthetic limbs, or adapted ski poles.
 - ✓ Sitting skiers, who use sit-skis or mono-skis and may require outriggers for balance and control.
- **Disciplines included:** All five alpine skiing disciplines are featured in para-alpine skiing competitions:
 - ✓ Slalom
 - ✓ Giant Slalom
 - ✓ Super-G (Super Giant Slalom)
 - ✓ Downhill
 - ✓ Super Combined (a mix of speed and technical events)
- **Specialized equipment:**
 - ✓ Sit-skis / Mono-skis – used by athletes with lower-limb impairments.
 - ✓ Outriggers – adapted forearm crutches with ski tips attached, used for balance and turning.
 - ✓ Ski guides – for visually impaired athletes, offering navigation and pacing support.
 - ✓ Adaptive prosthetics and orthotic gear – for standing skiers, depending on individual needs.
- **Complementary Benefits for Para-Alpine Skiing**
 - **Accessibility through innovation:** With ongoing advancements in adaptive equipment and individualized coaching, para-alpine skiing continues to expand its inclusivity.
 - **Elite performance and recognition:** Para-alpine skiing is a Paralympic sport, offering athletes the opportunity to compete at the highest international levels.
 - **Physical and mental resilience:** The sport demands not only physical strength and coordination but also courage, discipline, and quick decision-making, fostering overall personal development.
 - **Outdoor engagement and adventure:** Skiing in natural mountainous environments offers therapeutic, emotional, and sensory benefits, reinforcing a sense of freedom and accomplishment.

17. Showdown (Table Tennis for the Blind and Visually Impaired)

Showdown is a fast-paced, competitive sport specifically developed for individuals who are blind or visually impaired. Often described as a cross between table tennis and air hockey, it emphasizes sound-based play, quick reflexes, and spatial awareness. Designed for inclusivity and equality, all players—regardless of visual capacity—wear blacked-out goggles

to ensure a level playing field. This sport promotes concentration, coordination, and competitive engagement for athletes with visual impairments at both recreational and elite levels.

• Example of activities:

- **Game format:** Showdown is a two-player sport played on a specially designed table with an elongated oval shape and 14 cm high side walls. A center board divides the table and serves as an auditory barrier under which the ball must be hit.
- **Sound-based tracking:** The ball used in showdown is hard and contains built-in noisemakers (such as ball bearings), allowing players to locate it and react purely by sound.
- **Equipment:**
 - ✓ Blacked-out goggles – worn by all players to eliminate any visual advantage.
 - ✓ Rectangular paddle – used to strike the ball under the center board.
 - ✓ Protective gloves and guards – often used to prevent hand injuries during fast-paced play.
- **Scoring system:** Players aim to score by getting the ball into the opponent's goal slot located at either end of the table. The game is usually played to 11 or 21 points, depending on competition level.
- **Classification:** While all athletes play under the same visual conditions (completely blindfolded), classification systems may be used in official competitions to group players based on their overall level of visual impairment and additional functional criteria.

Complementary Benefits for Showdown (Table Tennis for the Blind and Visually Impaired)

- **Equal opportunity competition:** The use of blindfolds creates total parity among players, allowing athletes with partial or total vision loss to compete fairly.
- **Enhanced sensory development:** Players improve auditory processing, spatial orientation, and fine motor coordination.
- **Inclusive and accessible:** Showdown can be played in schools, rehabilitation centers, and clubs with minimal setup, making it highly adaptable to different spaces.
- **International recognition:** Showdown is governed by the International Blind Sports Federation (IBSA) and is increasingly present in international competitions and development programs for blind sports.

18. Deaf Tennis

Deaf tennis is an adapted form of standard tennis designed for athletes with hearing impairments. While the core rules and equipment remain virtually identical to those of traditional tennis, the game is shaped by the unique communication and perceptual needs of deaf players. With an emphasis on visual awareness and non-verbal coordination, deaf tennis fosters

10. EXAMPLES OF ADAPTED PHYSICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

inclusivity, independence, and athletic performance for individuals who experience hearing loss. The sport offers both recreational opportunities and elite-level competition through structured events like the Deaflympics and World Championships.

• Example of activities:

- **Standard tennis rules:** Deaf tennis follows the same scoring system, match structure, and court dimensions as regular tennis. The ball, racket, and net are identical to those used in mainstream tennis.
- **Communication methods:** In doubles play, athletes use visual cues and hand signals for coordination instead of verbal communication. Eye contact and physical gestures are essential.
- **Adaptations for hearing loss:**
 - ✓ Players with at least 55 dB hearing loss in the better ear are eligible to compete.
 - ✓ Hearing aids and cochlear implants are not permitted during official matches to ensure equal conditions.
- **Events and formats:** Competitions are held in singles, doubles, and team formats, across junior and adult categories. Major events include:
 - ✓ The Deaflympics – the highest level of competition for deaf athletes.
 - ✓ World Deaf Tennis Championships
 - ✓ Regional and national deaf tournaments recognized by the International Committee of Sports for the Deaf (ICSD).

Complementary Benefits for Deaf Tennis

- **Visual and spatial development:** Due to reliance on sight rather than sound, deaf players sharpen visual tracking, action time, and spatial coordination.
- **Improved balance and body control:** Inner ear impairments can affect balance, but deaf athletes often develop excellent proprioception and body awareness as compensation.
- **Social inclusion:** Deaf tennis creates an environment where players can connect with peers who share similar experiences, promoting self-esteem, confidence, and community.
- **Bridging communities:** While integration into mainstream training environments can pose challenges, deaf athletes in tennis often act as bridges between hearing and non-hearing sports communities.

CONCLUSION

Each of these adapted sport and physical activities can be implemented and customized to meet the needs of each person with a disability. Encouraging participation in sports and physical activities not only improves physical health, but also contributes significantly to mental and social well-being, increasing inclusion and self-confidence.

11. PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

Physical activity not only brings physical benefits, but also has a significant impact on the psychological and emotional state of people with disabilities. By improving self-esteem, combating isolation and managing stress, sport can become a powerful tool to support mental health and social integration.

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The impact of physical activity on self-esteem and confidence

Participation in physical activity can significantly improve the self-esteem and self-confidence of people with disabilities. Sport provides not only physical but also psychological benefits by creating a sense of achievement, autonomy and empowerment.

1. Creating a sense of personal achievement

When a person with a disability succeeds in achieving a sporting goal, no matter how small, the experience contributes directly to improved self-esteem. In this sense, success in physical activities becomes a catalyst for building confidence in one's own abilities.

- **Example:** A participant with a motor disability who manages to lift a heavier weight than before or completes an easy run may experience a sense of pride and accomplishment. This accomplishment contributes to increased self-confidence and the ability to overcome challenges.

2. Reduced perception of vulnerability

Physical activities can help people with disabilities to overcome their perceived limitations. By developing physical skills and making progress, people with disabilities can change their perspective about their limitations and increase their confidence in their ability to overcome difficulties.

- **Example:** For a person with cognitive disabilities, the simple fact that they can learn and improve the technique of a flexibility or balance exercise can help to increase their confidence and sense of control over their abilities

Fighting isolation and encouraging socialization through sport

People with disabilities often face social isolation, either because of stigmatization or because of difficulties of accessibility to social events. Sport is an excellent opportunity to overcome these barriers by creating a framework in which social interactions are promoted.

1. Creating an inclusive social environment

Participation in physical activities can help people with disabilities to interact with other people in an open and supportive environment. Sport becomes a space where participants can build relationships and friendships and social interactions become more natural.

- **Example:** In a fitness group adapted for people with a physical disability, participants can bond friendships through shared exercises. Teamwork or friendly competitions can encourage mutual support and reduce feelings of isolation.

2. Creating a sense of belonging

Participating in a sport or physical activity in a group can help create a sense of belonging. People with disabilities who are involved in an active and supportive group can learn to appreciate diversity and more easily express their needs and wishes.

- **Example:** In a volleyball or basketball team for people with disabilities, every member contributes to the team's success. Even in competitions, the fact that everyone is equally accepted and encouraged helps to integrate each and every participant.

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Managing stress and anxiety through exercise

Sport is a powerful tool for managing stress and anxiety. Physical activity helps to reduce levels of cortisol, the hormone associated with stress, and increase the production of endorphins, the 'happy' hormones that induce a general feeling of well-being.

1. Reduce symptoms of anxiety

Exercise can help manage symptoms of anxiety, as physical movement regulates adrenaline levels and reduces tension in the body. In addition, focusing on the correct execution of exercises helps to relax the mind and eliminate worry.

- **Example:** A participant with a disability who feels stressed due to daily pressures may benefit from a yoga or stretching session to relax. Focus on breathing and movement can help calm the mind and reduce feelings of panic or anxiety.

11. PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

2. Creating a mental and physical balance

Physical activities, such as walking, swimming or cycling, can help maintain a balance between body and mind. For people with disabilities, this balance is essential to prevent mental fatigue and increase overall well-being.

- **Example:** Playing a team sport or participating in group exercises, which include coordination and collaboration, can help participants to reduce anxiety and better manage their emotions.

Promoting a positive attitude

Sport not only brings physical benefits, but can profoundly influence your mindset and attitude to life. Participating in physical activities in a supportive group can help people with disabilities develop a positive attitude towards everyday challenges.

1. Improved motivation and perseverance

Physical activities help develop an attitude of perseverance and resilience. Even in the face of difficulties, sport can encourage the participant to maintain motivation and overcome obstacles, as progress is possible through constant practice.

- **Example:** A participant with a motor disability who has difficulty performing a movement can be encouraged by the instructor to keep practicing, even if progress is slower. This develops a 'perseverance' mindset, helping him/her to remain positive in the face of challenges.

2. Create a framework of encouragement and support

When people are supported and encouraged in a physical environment, this is reflected in their attitude to the challenges of everyday life. Participants who are recognized for their progress and receive constant support will develop a more positive attitude towards themselves and their own ability to cope with difficulties.

- **Example:** In a fitness group for people with disabilities, instructors can emphasize each person's progress, for example, "Even if you haven't reached your end goal, working steadily will get you better results. Keep focusing on the small steps and you will succeed!"

CONCLUSION: Sport as a psychological enhancer

Physical activities have a significant impact on the psychological health of people with disabilities. By improving self-esteem, combating social isolation, managing stress and developing a positive attitude, sport can contribute to the integration and development of people with disabilities in a holistic way. These psychological benefits are essential for the quality of life and can increase participants' autonomy and sense of achievement.

12. CONTINUOUS EVALUATION AND ADJUSTMENT OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PROGRAMS

On-going assessment of participants' progress is essential to ensure a process of constant adaptation of physical activity programs and to provide appropriate support according to everyone's needs and progress. This involves careful monitoring of physical and mental progress and continuous adjustment of the exercise program to meet the changing needs of participants. It is important that the assessment process is objective and individualized, and that adjustments are made in a way that supports progress without jeopardizing the person's safety or comfort.

Evaluation methods

The evaluation of the progress can be carried out by different methods, which provide clear and detailed information about the participant's condition and allow to adjust the programs in an efficient way.

1. Questionnaires and interviews:

Questionnaires and interviews are essential methods to understand participants' experiences and perceptions of physical activities. They help to obtain direct and honest feedback on the comfort and effectiveness of exercise, which can guide the program adjustment process.

◦ **Example:** A questionnaire may include questions such as:

- "How do you feel after physical activities?"
- "Did you feel any pain or discomfort during exercise? If so, where?"
- "Which exercise did you find hardest or easiest?"
- "What types of activities would you like to do more often?"

This feedback can help identifying possible physical discomforts, emotional needs, as well as adjustments to activities that enhance participants' engagement and motivation.

2. Physical measurements:

Physical tests are another valuable tool for assessing progress. Measures such as mobility, strength and endurance tests allow an objective assessment of physical skills and progress. They are essential to understand whether the program is effective and to determine whether adjustments need to be made according to the participant's physical progress.

◦ **Example:** In the case of a person with motor impairments, the range of movement of joints can be assessed by a flexibility test (e.g. measuring the flexion angle of a knee or elbow). Strength tests can also be performed to assess muscular endurance and the ability to perform strength exercises, such as lifting weights or using elastic bands. Monitoring these indicators will help tracking progress and correctly adjust exercise intensity.

3. Feedback from therapists or doctors:

Collaboration with health professionals (physicians, physical therapists) is crucial in the assessment process. They can provide a detailed assessment of the participant's health status and physical abilities, allowing programs to be adjusted to meet the participant's medical needs.

◦ **Example:** A therapist might notice that a participant with mobility impairments has limited joint mobility and recommend the use of gentle stretching exercises or aquatic activities to help improve flexibility without putting pressure on the joints. Feedback from a doctor will also help avoid overtraining, especially for people with chronic conditions (e.g. arthritis or cardiovascular disease).

12. CONTINUOUS EVALUATION AND ADJUSTMENT OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PROGRAMS

Adjusting physical activity programs

Adjusting physical activity programs is an ongoing process, which needs to respond to changes in the participant's health and abilities. Adjustments can be made based on feedback, assessment results and observed progress. Sometimes it may be necessary to completely change the type of exercise or the intensity of exercise to ensure the safety and effectiveness of the activities.

1. Change the type of exercise:

If a participant has difficulty in performing a particular type of exercise, or if an exercise is not suitable for his/her health condition, it is important to switch to alternatives that are more accessible or less demanding. Exercise should be adapted so that it can be performed comfortably and effectively.

- **Example:** If a person with a motor disability is unable to perform a strength exercise with weights, a trainer could replace exercises with weights with exercises using elastic bands. Elastic bands allow better control of the movement and are easier to use in a progressive way without the risk of overstraining joints or muscles.

2. Reduce exercise intensity:

If a participant is experiencing excessive fatigue or discomfort, it is essential to reduce exercise intensity or adjust it in order to prevent injury or over-exertion. A temporary reduction in intensity may also be necessary for a period of recovery.

- **Example:** If a person with a mobility impairment is unable to perform strenuous exercise, the intensity of activities may be reduced by shortening the duration of exercise sessions or concentrating on lighter exercises such as treadmill walking or swimming in a warm-water pool.

3. Exercise alternatives:

Sometimes some types of exercise are simply not appropriate for a particular participant. In these cases, it is important to identify a different type of physical activity that is more suitable and will help to improve health and achieve fitness goals.

- **Example:** Instead of a running exercise, which may be too demanding for a person with a motor disability, cycling on stationary bicycles or "cardio" activities in a swimming pool, where the movement is less demanding on the joints, may be chosen.

CONCLUSION

Through continuous and personalized adjustment of the physical activity programs, a constant improvement of the participant's health status and a promotion of an active and sustainable participation in physical activities is ensured. This assessment and adjustment process also contributes to maintaining an optimal level of motivation and commitment to exercise.

13. CASE STUDIES AND SUCCESS STORIES

Case 1: Physical activities for a person with cerebral palsy

A relevant example may be a case where a person with cerebral palsy (CP) participates in a physical activity program. In this case, the patient, a 28-year-old woman with a mild form of cerebral palsy, was experiencing difficulties with movement and coordination.

Intervention:

The program was adapted to include **active mobility exercises, muscle toning and balance exercises**. This was achieved through a personalized training plan that included:

- **Flexibility** exercises, with an instructor to guide movements.
- Upper body **strength exercises** using **small weights** or **elastic bands**.
- **Balance** activities such as sitting on a stabilizing ball.

Results:

After several months of constant training, the patient reported significant improvements in mobility and balance. She began to feel more confident in her ability to move short distances and was able to actively participate in group activities, such as adapted yoga exercises.

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Case 2: Athlete with hearing impairment

Another example could be a 22-year-old young man with total **hearing impairment** who wanted to participate in physical activities and team sports. Due to the absence of a clear communication strategy, his previous experiences in group sports were not successful.

Intervention:

In an **adapted program**, the instructor used **visual cues** to convey instructions, accompanied by **movement templates** to aid understanding of the steps in a sports game. **Technology** was also implemented to aid in communication (e.g., flashing lights or mobile apps with visual messaging).

Results:

The young man quickly learned the fundamentals of the game and began to actively participate in **adapted basketball** sessions where all participants were taught to use visual cues to communicate with each other.

Case 3: Aquatic activities for a person with a motor disability

A more complex example may be a 40-year-old man with a right **leg amputation** who wanted to improve mobility and increase self-confidence. **Swimming** activities were identified as an excellent solution due to the characteristics of the water providing a safe environment for training.

Intervention:

The aquatic activities program included **freestyle swimming** and **aqua fitness** exercises. The workouts were adapted to include **additional body support** using rafts or buoyancy devices. **Muscle toning** sessions for the upper body and improving **endurance** were also included.

Results:

After 3 months of the program, the man reported significant improvements in mobility, strength and coordination. In addition, he noted an increase in confidence in his abilities and participation in group activities helped him build valuable social relationships.

14. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

At the end of a manual aimed at people working with people with disabilities in physical activity and sport, it is essential to emphasize the importance of a continuous and adapted program to support their integration and development. In this section, we detail some key aspects that can contribute to the success of physical activities for people with disabilities, emphasizing the importance of monitoring, continuous adaptation and support for their integration.

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1. The importance of continuity and monitoring of physical activity

One of the most important aspects of physical activity for people with disabilities is continuity. It is essential that these participants have a constant exercise program to ensure a progressive and sustainable improvement in their physical and mental state.

- **Continuous progress monitoring:** Physical activities need to be constantly monitored to observe changes in performance and to adjust training plans. For example, progress in terms of mobility or resistance to fatigue should be assessed regularly and exercise intensity adjusted as improvements are observed.
 - **Practical example:** For a person with motor disabilities, monitoring might include regular assessment of joint mobility, fatigue and ability to perform strength exercises. Using an activity log can be a useful tool to document progress and identify possible areas needing adjustment.
- **The benefits of continuity:** Regular physical activity helps prevent complications associated with disability such as muscle atrophy, balance disorders, anxiety and depression. Continuing an adapted program also provides a sense of routine and security, which can contribute to increased self-confidence and quality of life.

2. Constantly adapt training to each person's progress

Another key aspect in physical activities for people with disabilities is flexibility and adapting workouts to participants' progress. Each person has their own pace of development and may face different challenges, which means that workouts need to be modified regularly to suit their individual needs.

- **Regular assessments:** Periodic assessments are fundamental to adjusting workouts. These can include testing mobility, strength, endurance, balance and coordination, as well as discussions with participants about their perceptions of any difficulties or improvements observed. This data can be used to adapt exercises and plan new goals.
 - **Practical example:** If a participant with a motor disability is progressing and gaining more arm strength, the coach can introduce more complex strength exercises using resistance equipment (elastic bands, light weights) to encourage continued progress. In turn, for a person with cognitive disabilities, it may be helpful to introduce smaller steps and a slower pace in each training session to avoid overtraining.
- **Personalize training for the long term:** It is important to adjust training not only for immediate physical progress, but also for long-term goals. If a participant wants to compete, training needs to become more intense and more specifically targeted to the skills needed for the sport, and these adjustments need to be made step by step.

14. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

3. Measures to support the integration of people with disabilities in sport and physical activities

The integration of people with disabilities in sport and physical activities is not limited to training sessions. It is essential to create an inclusive and supportive environment that enables these people to actively participate and feel part of the sporting community.

- **Creating an accessible and friendly environment:** Accessibility is a key factor. Training and event venues need to be adapted to meet the physical needs of people with disabilities (e.g. access ramps, halls with sufficient space for wheelchair maneuvering, accessible toilets). In addition, it is important that staff and teammates are trained to work with people with disabilities, have a positive attitude and support integration.
- **Promoting inclusive sports:** An important recommendation is that sports institutions and clubs promote inclusive sports that are open to all. This can include organizing competitions or events where people with and without disabilities participate together in order to encourage collaboration and mutual respect.
 - **Practical example:** Creating a community-wide wheelchair basketball tournament, where participants with and without disabilities are equipped and play together, encourages integration and removes mental barriers related to disability.
- **Staff training and education:** Sport and physical activity professionals need to be trained in the needs and abilities of people with disabilities in order to provide appropriate support and encourage their active participation. Such training may include techniques for adapting exercises, understanding disability and developing an inclusive attitude.
- **Psychological and social support:** In some cases, integration into physical and sporting activities is not only a physical challenge but also a psychological one. It is essential to provide psychological support, including counseling or support groups, to help people with disabilities to adapt and overcome fears or anxieties related to participation in sports.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

Adapted physical activities are essential for the well-being of people with disabilities, providing them with an opportunity to develop physically and mentally, to face challenges, to socialize and to improve their quality of life. Through continuity and regular monitoring of activities, constant adaptation of training and supporting their integration into the sporting community, long-term success can be ensured. It is important for society and sporting communities to support and include people with disabilities by creating environments that are accessible, respectful and provide equal opportunities for all.

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INSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

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